

EDUCASH

A Capstone Project

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College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

by

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The capstone project entitles:

EDUCASH

submitted by Von Andrei G. Awacay, Jhon Patrick B. Perez, and Jonh Lorence G. Reyes

have been examined and are recommended for Oral Defense.

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EduCash

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ABSTRACT

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 promotes inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Despite ongoing efforts, many college students in Bacolod City continue to experience financial hardship that limits access to higher education and academic continuity. In response, EduCash was developed as a web based financial assistance platform that connects underprivileged yet academically qualified students with donors, non-government organizations, and scholarship agencies. The system integrates scholarship matching, document verification, donor portals, and secure financial transaction modules supported by multiple digital payment gateways. Student eligibility is assessed through academic credentials and verification processes, while scholarship agencies manage postings and fund distribution through predefined calculation methods. The application also allows students to track the status of their scholarship applications in real time. Donors and scholarship agencies can monitor fund allocations and verify transactions securely. By integrating these features, EduCash ensures a reliable experience.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CONCEPTS

• Web-Based Application Development • Model-View-Controller (MVC) Architecture • Document Verification and Data Validation.

KEYWORDS

Underprivileged College Students, Data Analytics, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Calculations.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Education is a universal and transformative human right to boost development and empower individual growth and community development. Such an instrument is so far one of the greatest enablers to overcome this cycle of poverty as it addresses systemic inequalities at several levels. Education equips people with knowledge for skills, which plays an extremely important role to help increase health outcomes, support equal gender relations, spread peaceful coexistence, and sustainable social order. Education benefits are deep and broad. Economically, it provides tremendous and steady returns: higher incomes, better jobs, and the capacity to work in meaningful ways within the community. Socially, education is the foundation of equity, inclusion, and bridge the gaps between the different groups to give equal opportunities to everyone that came from all walks of life to be able to succeed [WWW01]. United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), Quality Education [WWW02], emphasizes this to ensure equitable and unexclusive quality education for everyone.

Bacolod City, a home to several colleges and universities for college students. Bacolod City is often called the "City of Smiles," and it is now boomed as a center for higher education in the Western Visayas region of the Philippines. The city has numerous colleges and universities that provide diverse academic opportunities to students all over the region. Such institutions promote an atmosphere of students who strive to achieve the best in users in the field of science and technology, arts, and social sciences. Students at Bacolod City College.

are committed to achieve the academic success, thereby make it possible the attainment of individual and career goals that are vital. However, many students who have enrolled with colleges in Bacolod city still face major financial constraints that limit them to pursue collegiate education. Tuition and regular expenses along with limited funds seriously burden students along with their families. Affected families are the most vulnerable to low-income statuses. Thus, there is a critical need for freely available scholarships, grants and other financial

aid that might help in overcome the obstacles of economic constraints to scholarly and professional goals of eager students

EduCash, a web-based application, aims to provide a solution for these obstacles faced by college students based in Bacolod City. Through a provision of a application for them that connects them with the Non-Government Organizations (NGO), as well as any other individuals who are eager to provide financial support, EduCash enables them to donate funds through scholarship agencies that are registered in the application, and these funds are disbursed to students later on. By means of the closure of the gap between donors and recipients. The inspiration of the development this application is to encourage the culture of eagerness and community support, as aligned with the mission for equitable education of SDG 4.

1.1 Project Scope

EduCash is a web-based application that aimed to financially assist college students that are underprivileged but qualified to benefit from the said financial assistance, through donation from NGO and other specific individuals who are eager to donate. EduCash only caters to college students that are currently academically based in Bacolod City. The following subsequent sections are the discussion that defines the project scope to identify the project requirements.

2 METHODOLOGY

The EduCash system focuses on creating an accessible and efficient web-based platform that supports real time interaction between underprivileged students, donors, and scholarship agencies. The system utilizes a centralized web application developed using PHP and MySQL under the Model View Controller architecture to manage user accounts, scholarship matching, document verification, and financial transactions. Core modules continuously process user submitted data such as academic records, eligibility requirements, and donation information, ensuring accurate evaluation and reliable system operations. This approach supports dependable data handling, secure transactions, and ease of use, particularly for users with limited technical resources. The web application serves as the primary interface, featuring intuitive dashboards and visual data representations through tables, graphs, and charts. Users monitor scholarship matches, donation summaries, and application statuses, while administrators track system performance and participation trends. The platform also supports data logging and export of reports for documentation and analysis purposes. In addition, EduCash includes informational sections that provide guidance on scholarship procedures, eligibility requirements, and financial assistance processes, promoting transparency, awareness, and informed participation among all stakeholders.

2.1 Design and Implementation Controls

In the implementation of this web-based application, there are no such systems that are able to do any act without boundaries. In systems development, constraints and difficulties are commonly encountered, such as user interface design. This section discusses the areas of concern in the development of the application.

2.2 Operating Environment

This web-based application supplicates funds from donors, specifically the NGO and other specific individuals who are eager to help in such a cause, enabled students to earn financial support that accords to user academic performance, to ensure increased motivation and engagement in user studies. To ensure a successful development phase, it is essential to identify the hardware and software specifications that supports these tools. This section outlines the requirements for the development and implementation of this project. The hardware requirements for development have been efficiently selected to guarantee optimal performance throughout the entire project with the least amount of time wasted. The perhaps most distinguished member of this list is the AMD Ryzen 5[WWW12], one of the fastest processors there is today, known for its speed and multitask potential. Such a CPU possesses immense power and efficiency to conduct functions like code compilation, administrated demand algorithms and debug tests, all while running the development workstation in the SAF environment. Its multi-core architecture, therefore, gives the much-needed capability of performance demand in resource applications, such as backend processes and online media applications, without to consume processed resources, thus promoted productivity by reduction of lag. To complement the process power, 8 GB of DDR4 RAM is included, which is just right for reliable memory support. This means developers are able to open multiple applications-such as IDEs, version control systems, virtual machines, and browsers for testing-at the same time and with enjoyable performance. The project team effortlessly drift into the code to be debugged and continue to be tested. Secondary storage that ranged from 256 GB to 512 GB SSD, provision to a broadened range of responsiveness. An SSD reduces the time taken to start up files and applications, and thus boots faster, reads and writes faster, and ultimately maximizes user experience. More useful in the phase of compilation and deployment since data and resource access is needed with extraordinary rapidity there. Table 3 illustrated the key software tools that are implemented that built the application and the collaboration processes involved. Integrated Environment: Visual Studio Code [WWW13] provides an Integrated IDE that has highly flexible and lightweight functionality in regard to the development and fix bugs. Git/GitHub [WWW15] are used for version control management in order to keep project files secure and provide team collaboration capabilities. PowerShell acts as an automation and

system maintenance scripting terminal for the project team. For front-end development, the project team intends to use Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and Bootstrap 5 alongside JavaScript for an interactive user interface. PHP is utilized to aid in the back-end development. MySQL is used for management in the back-end database. The application is deployed on the Windows 10 or higher workstation. Three modes of communication within the project team are utilized: Microsoft Teams, Discord, and Google. These modes allow complete interaction among members of the project team, plan sensitively, real-time coordination, and documentation.

Component	Software Tool
Integrated Development Environment (IDE)	Visual Code Studio
Version Control	Git/GitHub
Terminals	Power shell
Frontend Development	Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)/ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)/ JavaScript
Backend Development	PHP, MySQL
Operating System	Windows 10/11
Communication Applications	Microsoft Teams/ Discord
Collaboration Applications	Google Docs
Search Engine	Google Chrome
Prototyping	Figma
Frameworks and Libraries	BOOTSTRAP 5, jQuery
Engines	Tesseract OCR, PHP Mailer

Table 3. Software Requirements

2.3 Features and Functionalities

The five general features of the system are illustrated in the Figure 1 namely Allowance Distribution, Donor Portal, Scholarship Match, Data Analytics, and Document Verification. By the components presented, components that work together to form the performance process of the application, the project team planned and reviewed the specification to make sure that the development and initiation of the application is successful. Each feature is designed to focus on connection of a smooth transaction in the application. The project team aims to seamlessly integrate these features to guarantee a user-friendly and an efficient application for donors and recipients. The development process involves detailed plan and repetitive test to make sure that each feature meet the needs of users effectively. As shown in the sections followed and its subsequent sections in this chapter discusses the assumptions and dependencies, understand comprehensively and analysis of the project facilitated its development. These features serve as the foundation of the systems overall functionality and operational

flow. The integration of these components ensures that processes within the application are coordinated and properly managed.

Figure 1: EduCash General Features

The Donor Portal feature provided donors a way to contribute monetarily to support the goals of the project through payment integrations of bank system as one time or repeated donors on the scholarship agencies to support. Donors are also able to donate through payment gateways that is integrated in the application such as PayPal, Gcash, and Maya. Individual donors have the decision to keep themselves as anonymous donors for those who value privacy and does not want to be acknowledged. This feature also provides the donors the proof of user donation through acknowledgement receipt that is generated by the application. The acknowledgement receipt includes the purpose of user transaction which is to donate. The receipt provides the donor a view of user transaction such as the amount of user donation, on what agency the donor has donated and the time and date of the transaction. The Scholarship Matching feature provided the students smooth and faster inquiries of scholarships existed that cater to students that are academically based in Bacolod city, users are able to provide information necessary to apply for a scholarship included users credentials and performance at school. After which, the system is able to provide them the scholarship agency on which users credentials are matched. This feature also assists scholarship agencies to find applicants that are qualified students who meet user criteria and user specific requirements. The requirements that are set by the scholarship agencies in the application that the students fill out, serve only as a screening process and not a direct way that the students be considered as an official applicant of user program, only the approval for further transactions are sent to students as a notification. The data analytics feature displayed in a dashboard consists of the data such as total amount of donations gathered, total number of applicants, total number of NGO donors, which are represented in a bar graph, and a pie chart of the percentage of the individual and anonymous donors. This feature serves as a significant element for evaluation of the performance of the application. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the application. Specifically, the application provides an analyzation and display key metrics that are

discussed further in this section of the paper. In Allowance Distribution feature, the students are able to claim financial aid calculated by the application through payment gateways integrated in the application. The distribution is scheduled on a specific month each semester and each time before the distribution, students must submit the reports of their academic performance. Students must maintain their academic performance as based in the eligibility criteria to avoid being classified dropped as an applicant of the scholarship agency. When the general average fall below the criteria set by the scholarship agency, this allows them to disqualify the applicant to avail the provisions from the scholarship agencies and the student is not able to match with the scholarship agency for the next period of disbursement until criteria is matched again. Lastly, the Document Verification feature arguably becomes one of the great features incorporated into the application to sustain the originality and authenticity of the submission of the users. It is the defense that protects the integrity of the application against schemes such as fraudulent submissions and misrepresentation. This set of operations protects the integrity of the identity of the applicants and other assertions in more thorough verification to prove that he or she is an ethically and legitimately acceptable candidate for the benefited service. It validates uploads from supported documents, academic records, financial statements, and identity proofs through stringent loopholes verification. The system further minimizes errors for it to check every document against a reliable database while engaged in good security services aimed at caught attempts of crashes and forgeries

2.4 Interfaces and Interactions.

The user interfaces of the EduCash application are the gateway through which donors, students, and scholarship agencies together with the admin interact with one another. The user interfaces encompass the interactive and visual elements that enabled the seamless access to features and navigation. This section of the chapter explores the principles, usability, and the layout that ensures an intuitive and engaging user experience. EduCash provided a color-coded interface depending on the user types to prevent confusion and by consolidating the background color to identify different account types such as donors, scholarship agencies, and students.

When the donor clicks on the donate section on the side navigation bar, the donor then is redirected to the form where the donate feature is accessible using the form to fill out. The donors are able to search by filling out the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement required in the scholarship agency and click on the search button. Below the form is the list of the verified scholarship agencies. As shown in the Figure 1, the interface displays the profile picture and the name of the scholarship agency that are verified by the admin and criteria are set for matching.

Figure 1. Donor Portal

As shown in Figure 2, the reports and dashboard interface presents a structured and visually organized screen layout designed to provide users with clear and meaningful insights into the system data. When the user selects the Reports button from the sidebar section, the system redirects the user to a dedicated dashboard page that consolidates all analytical graphs and reports generated by the application. This interface serves as a centralized monitoring tool for administrators and authorized users, allowing them to assess system performance and participation trends at a glance. The first visual component displayed on the dashboard is a pie chart that illustrates the distribution of donor types within the system. This chart presents the proportional representation of contributors, including non-government organizations, anonymous donors, government agencies, private companies, and specific individual donors. By categorizing donor participation, the chart highlights the diversity of support sources that willingly contribute to assisting underprivileged and deserving students. The second component is a line chart that displays the cumulative number of student beneficiaries added to the system on a monthly basis. This visualization allows users to observe growth patterns in student participation over time, identify periods of increased enrollment, and assess the overall reach of the platform. Lastly, the dashboard includes a bar graph that represents the total amount of donations collected each month. This graph provides a clear comparison of donation trends over time, enabling users to evaluate fundraising performance, identify peak donation periods, and support data driven decision making.

Figure 2. Data Analytics Reports

Upon clicking on the scholarship section on the side navigation bar, the student is redirected into the page where scholarships that matched with the credentials are displayed. As shown in Figure 3 are the scholarship agencies that matched with the qualifications and living conditions of the students. The interface also shows the deadline of application and the profile photo of the scholarship agency.

Figure 3. Scholarship Matching

Once a student is already registered and has logged in to an existing student account, the student is then redirected to the form where necessary documents and files is uploaded and is validated by the application. The students are required to upload the certificate of enrolment, validated school ID, and the certified true copy of grades for the application to verify that the user is currently enrolled. To verify that the student is in need or underprivileged when it comes to the financial aspect, some documents are required to submit which is the certificate of indigency and the proof of income of the parents of the students. The application aims only to support the students that are underprivileged but is deserving and has commendable performance in education. The uploaded documents are carefully reviewed and validated by the application to ensure accuracy and eligibility before proceeding with the scholarship matching process. The validation supports the application in identifying eligible students based on the required documents.

Figure 4. Document Verification

After selecting a calculation method, scholarship agencies are now able to disburse the money to the students with a guide of the amount and the number of students. As shown in Figure 5, the total amount of donations and the total number of students are visible. A button with a bank icon is visible as an action that when clicked, it redirects the page to the payment gateways interface.

Figure 5. Allowance Distribution

3 PERFORMANCE TESTING EVALUATION.

This section of the paper discusses how the EduCash application performed its functionalities and features effectively and efficiently. In evaluating the performance of the application, many measures were used and implemented to solve its coefficient, which helped the project team to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the application to perform more efficiently. The software quality attributes were used to evaluate the features of the application. EduCash had four major functionalities, such as Account Creation

and Management, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Financial Transactions, and Data Analytics.

The software quality model, ISO 25010 [ISO25], was used as reference to evaluate the system features of EduCash application. Five leading quality attributes such as Security, Usability, Reliability, Performance Efficiency, and Maintainability, were used to examine and evaluate the feature of the application. The project team evaluated the authentication process which included the login and registration for security to ensure that the application safely keep the information of the users. The security attribute included the following criteria to be used such as confidentiality, Integrity, Accountability, and Authenticity. As for the Scholarship Matching, the quality attribute was used to evaluate its performance for the matches of student profiles and scholarship agencies. As for the financial transactions, For the Financial Transactions module, the primary quality attribute is Security, specifically focusing on Integrity, based on the ISO/IEC 25010 model. Integrity ensures that all donation and scholarship fund transactions are processed and stored without unauthorized alteration, duplication, or loss. This guarantees the correctness and trustworthiness of financial records, which is essential for maintaining donor confidence and ensuring fair distribution of scholarship funds. For the Data Analytics module of EduCash, the primary quality attribute is Accuracy, under the Functional Suitability category of ISO/IEC 25010. Accuracy ensures that the analytical output such as applicant statistics, donor contributions, scholarship demand, and matching outcomes correctly represent the underlying system data. This guarantees trustworthy insights for students, agencies, and administrators, enabling reliable decision-making based on accurate quantitative results.

System Features	Software Quality Attributes and Models	Software Quality Criteria	Mean Score	Feature Mean Score
Account Creation and Management	Security	Integrity	50%	62.5%
		Confidentiality	75%	
		Authenticity	62.5%	
Scholarship Matching and Postings	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	91.7%
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	100%	
Financial Transactions	Security	Integrity	83%	83.23%
		Confidentiality	100%	
		Authenticity	66.7%	
Calculations	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	80.6
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	66.7%	

Table 2. Summary of Features, Attributes, and Results

and their corresponding interpretations for the feature mean scores. It helps explain the derived quality scores and enables the project team to assess the performance of the system features based on its attributes. A percentage range of 84.1%-100% is marked as the highest rate a feature is able to receive, while having a 36% as the lowest rate.

Table 3. Mean Score Interpretation

3.1 Integrity

The software quality attribute that ensures that computer programs and data are protected from unauthorized access or modification, maintaining accuracy, consistency, and trustworthiness. Using Formula 1, the mean integrity score was calculated by dividing the number of resolved requirements by the total number of requirements, providing a quantitative measure of the system's ability to preserve its intended state against potential threats or errors.

$$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}}$$

Formula 1. Integrity Formula

3.2 Confidentiality

The software quality attribute that ensures that data are accessible only to authorized users, protecting sensitive information from unauthorized access, modification, or exploitation. The evaluation of confidentiality was quantified using a formula that divided the number of resolved confidentiality requirements by the total number of requirements, providing a clear measure of how effectively the system met its security objectives.

$$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 2. Confidentiality Formula

3.3 Authenticity

The software quality attribute that refers to the degree to which a user identity is verified as truly belonging to the individual claiming it. Assessed using Formula 3, the authenticity metric was calculated by dividing the number of resolved functions by the total number of requirements, providing a quantitative measure of how effectively the system verifies and validates user identities.

$$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 3. Authenticity Formula

3.4 Correctness

The software quality attribute that refers to the degree to which a system produces accurate and reliable results, as demonstrated in Formula 4. The correctness metric was calculated by dividing the number of successfully implemented functions by the total number of functions, providing a quantitative measure of how effectively the system meets its functional requirements.

$$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 4. Correctness Formula

3.5 Completeness

The software quality attribute that reflects the degree to which a system's functions satisfy all user goals and specified tasks. Using Formula 5, the mean completeness score was calculated by dividing the number of requirements met by the total number of requirements, providing a quantitative measure of how thoroughly the system fulfills its intended purpose.

$$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 5. Completeness Formula

3.6 Consistency

The software quality attribute that reflects the degree to which system functions behave uniformly and reliably across all operations. Using Formula 6, the consistency mean score was calculated by dividing the number of consistent functions by the total number of specified functions and multiplying the result by 100, providing a quantitative measure of the system's reliability and predictability.

$$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 6. Consistency Formula

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this capstone provides a summary of the solutions developed to address the financial challenges faced by underprivileged yet academically qualified college students in Bacolod City through the EduCash application. This section consolidates the results obtained during the development and evaluation phases and emphasizes the system's overall

functionality and effectiveness. Its objective is to present a clear and comprehensive overview of the project findings and outcomes, demonstrating the application's effectiveness in delivering transparent financial assistance, scholarship matching, and user support.

4.1 Conclusion

EduCash effectively achieves the objectives outlined in its design and implementation by providing a comprehensive web-based platform that supports underprivileged yet academically qualified college students in Bacolod City. The system integrates secure financial processes, scholarship management, and user-friendly interfaces to promote transparency and accessibility. Overall, the application demonstrates its effectiveness as a reliable solution for educational financial assistance.

4.1.1 System development: A web-based application was developed to connect students, donors, and scholarship agencies. The system was designed to ensure secure user authentication, efficient data handling, and role-based access for different user types.

4.1.2 Donor Portal: The donor portal enables various donors to provide financial support through secure and integrated payment gateways. Transaction records and generated receipts enhance transparency and allow donors to track their contributions.

4.1.3 Scholarship Matching: The system implements scholarship matching by evaluating student academic performance and eligibility requirements defined by scholarship agencies. It supports structured allowance distribution using predefined calculation methods to ensure fair allocation of funds.

4.1.4 Data Analytics: The system provides dashboards that visualize donation trends, applicant statistics, and scholarship distributions using graphs and charts. These visual tools support monitoring and evaluation of system performance by authorized users.

4.1.5 Document verification: The system validates academic, financial, and identity records to maintain system integrity and prevent fraudulent submissions. The verification process ensures that only qualified and legitimate applicants are considered for financial assistance.

In conclusion, EduCash presents a system that incorporates secure financial transactions, scholarship matching, data analytics and document verification aligning with the projects design objectives.

4.2 Recommendations

A good way to improve EduCash's efficiency and credibility is to implement a system-generated receipt feature that automatically validates transactions and

produces standardized digital receipts. By extracting and verifying transaction details from payment gateways and generating official receipts with unique identifiers and QR codes, the system can reduce manual processing, prevent fraudulent submissions, and strengthen financial transparency while improving donor satisfaction.

Another important enhancement is the full integration of payment gateways such as GCash, PayPal, and Maya directly into the EduCash platform. Embedding these gateways through official APIs enables real-time transaction confirmation, automated recording, and immediate receipt generation, resulting in a faster, more seamless donation experience and eliminating errors caused by manual receipt uploads and delayed verification.

Lastly, enforcing a one student, one scholarship agency policy ensures fair and equitable distribution of financial aid across beneficiaries. By limiting students to a single active scholarship at a time, the system prevents resource hoarding, simplifies fund tracking, promotes ethical allocation of support, and maximizes the platform's overall social impact by assisting a greater number of deserving students.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Education is a universal and transformative human right to boost development and empower individual growth and community development. Such an instrument is so far one of the greatest enablers to overcome this cycle of poverty as it addresses systemic inequalities at several levels. Education equips people with knowledge for skills, which plays an extremely important role to help increase health outcomes, support equal gender relations, spread peaceful coexistence, and sustainable social order. Education benefits are deep and broad. Economically, it provides tremendous and steady returns: higher incomes, better jobs, and the capacity to work in meaningful ways within the community. Socially, education is the foundation of equity, inclusion, and bridge the gaps between the different groups to give equal opportunities to everyone that came from all walks of life to be able to succeed [WWW01]. United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), Quality Education [WWW02], emphasizes this to ensure equitable and unexclusive quality education for everyone.

Bacolod City, a home to several colleges and universities for college students. Bacolod City is often called the "City of Smiles," and it is now boomed as a center for higher education in the Western Visayas region of the Philippines. The city has numerous colleges and universities that provide diverse academic opportunities to students all over the region. Such institutions promote an atmosphere of students who strive to achieve the best in users into the field of science and technology, arts, and social sciences. Students at Bacolod City College.

are committed to achieve the academic success, thereby make it possible the attainment of individual and career goals that are vital. However, many students who have enrolled with colleges in Bacolod city still face major financial constraints that limit them to pursue collegiate education. Tuition and regular expenses along with limited funds seriously burden students along with their families. Affected families are the most vulnerable to low-income statuses. Thus, there is a critical need for freely available scholarships, grants and other financial aid that might help in overcome the obstacles of economic constraints to scholarly and professional goals of eager students

EduCash, a web-based application, aims to provide a solution for these obstacles faced by college students based in Bacolod City. Through a provision of a application for them that connects them with the Non-Government Organizations (NGO), as well as any other individuals who are eager to provide financial support, EduCash enables them to donate funds through scholarship agencies that are registered in the application, and these funds are disbursed to students later on. By means of the closure of the gap between donors and recipients. The inspiration of the development this application is to encourage the culture of eagerness and community support, as aligned with the mission for equitable education of SDG 4.

1.1 Purpose

By supplication of funds from various donors and of provision an efficient transaction to scholarship agencies, the project aims to provide financial support to underprivileged yet qualified college students that are based in Bacolod City. In this section of the chapter, the project team has formulated three purposes of the EduCash project that

ultimately aims to bridge the gap in financial needs and educational opportunity. Purpose such as a application that connects recipients to donors, fast scholarship matching, and provision of calculations for the disbursement of the money to the college students that are based in Bacolod City. The subsequent sections below are the discussions of the three purposes of the application.

1.1.1 Application for Donors and Recipients

The application is composed of a number of actors which comprise individual donors, private or government agencies, as well as several NGO and scholarship agencies who are eager to render support and make contributions for the good cause that the application wanted to embody. Basically, the main objective of the application is to provide a centralized space for donors to render basic financial assistance to needy students who show great promise and deserve opportunities for academic success while students are still academically based in Bacolod City. To achieve such objective, the application set up some criteria and conditions which the students must have meet to be qualified and have access to the system included to keep satisfactory grades and other forms of commendable academic performance. Conditions are monitored each semester, to ensure that the students still qualified to be granted financial support from donors and still be a recipient in the application.

1.1.2 Calculated Cash Disbursements

By the supplication of monetary donations from NGOs and individual donors who are eager to support the application, EduCash aims to provide a calculated cash disbursement to each scholarship agency. This disbursement

serves as a guideline for how the agencies allocate the donations over a specified period to student recipients. Such an approach promoted systematic fund distribution, enhances financial oversight, and ensures congruence with the temporal and economic needs of the beneficiaries.

1.1.3 Scholarship Matching

The application is linked to scholarship agencies with the college student recipients that are academically based in Bacolod City. The application is able to provide scholarship agencies an access to the application where users are able to publish opportunities and directly interact with the applicants and also acted as the primary recipient of the money to be disbursed to the students. As for the students, the purpose of this is to provide them fast inquiries in scholarship agencies and application. Students are able to match with the scholarship agencies that match user credentials and academic performance efficiently by to filter some criteria. Another purpose of this is to guarantee that qualified students are able to match quickly with the scholarship suitable to them.

1.2 Technical Review of Related Systems

EduCash is an application of donation specifically designed to aid underprivileged and qualified college students that are academically based in Bacolod City. Different from other general donation systems like Give Lively [WWW03], Donorbox[WWW04], and GoFundMe [WWW05], that cater to wide range of purposes, the EduCash application centers exclusively on educational support through monetary donations. The application takes into employment of the eligibility criteria- based selection that aims to guarantee that

only the students who meet the need of financial aid and specific academic requirements. This appends a component of accountability, and transparency that is frequently missed by larger fundraising applications. Moreover, EduCash permits closer engagement between donors such as NGO, and individual or anonymous donors, and recipients which are the underprivileged college students academically based in Bacolod City, offered a unique opportunity for donors to track the progress of the students the donor supports. These systems mentioned above existed and has influenced the project included the functions that allowed the system to act as a application between donors and recipients. However, there are differences between EduCash and these systems. Illustrated in Table 1 are the criteria to identify the divergences between related systems and the discussion of each systems mentioned.

Application /Criteria	Give Lively	Donorbox	GoFundMe	EduCash
Payment Gateways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PayPal ○ All major Credit Cards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Google Pay ○ Apple Pay ○ Paypal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ All Major Credit Card ○ PayPal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Paypal ○ GCash ○ Maya
Data Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Non-profit's EIN ○ Email Verification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Automated Receipts ○ Endorsements and Certifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identity Verification ○ Fraud Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Email Verification ○ Document Verification
Security Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SSL ○ Database Encryption ○ PCI Compliance ○ Underpinned by industry leading partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fraud Detection and monitoring tokenization ○ PCI Compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fraud Detection ○ Data Encryption ○ PCI Compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Secured Remittance ○ User-authentication ○ Data Protection
Donor Portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create,edit, or update account ○ Donation History ○ List of Repeated Donors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receipts ○ Manage repeated donations ○ Profile Information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create Profile ○ Track Donations ○ Access campaign updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Donor Profiles ○ Agency Profiles

Table 1. Comparative Matrix of Related Systems.

1.2.1 Payment Gateway

This criterion referred to the available methods for donors to process financial donations which users are able to donate to different causes or organizations. The systems Give Lively, Donorbox, and GoFundMe utilized their own set of payment methods to ensure donors contribute securely, and to use users' preferred transaction method. Give Lively allows donors to donate via PayPal [WWW06], reducing the difficulty for people who already have PayPal accounts to donate without the need to re-enter payment information. Donors are also able to use credit/debit card payments. Give Lively offers transparency with a donation receipt that is automatically sent to the email address of the donor. In addition, Give Lively also accepts all major credit cards in the payment gateways of users. On the other hand, Donorbox offers a larger array of payment methods than Give Lively. Modern payment methods such as Apple Pay [WWW07], and Google Pay [WWW08] are utilized by Donorbox, providing a wide range of options for donors who prefer solutions such as mobile or digital wallet, which is more popular because of its user-friendly and security features. In addition, Donorbox allows donors to donate via PayPal through all major credit cards in users' payment gateways.

As for EduCash, the application seamlessly integrates multiple payment gateways that are included such as PayPal, Maya [WWW09], and GCash [WWW10], in addition to bank payment integrations used in a bank Application Programming Interface (API). This multi-faceted payment system allows the donors to easily contribute monetarily to qualified students, offered

them a range of convenient and secure payment options. With these diverse channels, EduCash ensures that the donors are able to donate and contribute effortlessly, regardless of users preferred method, thus fostered a wider reach to support the needs of the students.

1.2.2 Data Validation

This criterion referred to the procedure that the systems used to guarantee the validity and legitimacy of the provided data throughout the donation process. Effective data validation assists to ward off fraud, and to guarantee with the legal standards. In Give Lively, the application uses Employer Identification Numbers (EIN) to identify nonprofit organizations to verify nonprofit status that allows the application to confirm a tax-exempt status of an organization. To ensure the compliance and transparency, EIN provides the application an aid to verify that the organization or the nonprofit meets the legal standards for accountability and tax exemption. However, Donorbox approach offers more sophisticated data set of validation tools compared to Give Lively. Donorbox utilizes automated receipts to ensure that the proof of contribution is immediately received by the donors, which helped the system to verify the legitimacy of campaigns and donations. This focus on validation is crucial, given the open nature of GoFundMe, where anyone is enabled to create campaigns for various purposes.

As for EduCash, the application implements a more targeted set of validation measures. This measure includes donor, student grades, and document verification. This comprehensive validation process is essential for the mission of EduCash. These measures aimed to ensure that the donations reach genuinely

college students studying in Bacolod City who meet specific academic performance and financial criteria.

1.2.3 Security Measures

This criterion referred to the security metrics of each application employed to protect sensitive data, user information, and financial transactions. Stated the nature of online donations, a strong security protocols are necessary to protect against data breaches, fraud, and other cyber threats. These metrics helps the integrity of the application. Give Lively security measure creates a safe space where users feel confident user data is protected. First, it uses end-to-end encryption and Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)-protected pages to make sure that information stays secure and private while it traveled between users and the application—no inquisitive eyes allowed. Second, data storage is handled thoughtfully. Only essential data are stored, and it is encrypted within the database to keep it safe even if the system is breached. The system do not keep data longer than needed, which minimizes risks. Give Lively also partners with top industry players who help ensure all runs smoothly and securely, so users do not have to worry about outages or vulnerabilities. Finally, through multiple partners, maintain PCI Level 1 Compliance, the gold standard in payment security, protected payment data from potential fraud. Donorbox on the other hand, integrates a large-scale array of security features, protected financial and user data. Just like Give Lively, Donorbox also provides two-factor authentication(2FA) and Fraud detection as security metrics. In addition, Donorbox make use of tokenization to increase the security of transactions. Donorbox also make use of Secure Socket Layer/Transport Layer

Security Encryption, to guarantee the data that are transmitted between the donor and the application is securely encrypted, prevented intruders or interception by malicious actors. Donorbox embedded a fraud detection system into the application, scan for unusual patterns and block suspicious activities.

Additionally, Donorbox added ReCAPTCHA [WWW11] to Identify and differentiate real users from automated systems. ReCAPTCHA aids in the reduction of unauthorized card test, which in turn help limit chargeback fees. GoFundMe on the other hand, Integrated fraud detection, data encryption, and PCI compliance for protected user data and to guarantee transactions that are safe. Moreover, GoFunMe also focuses on security but with measures specifically adjusted to ensure remittance security, user authentication, SSL encryption, and PCI compliance. The application puts an emphasis on secure remittance as well as data protection that shields sensitive information, particularly in a student-centered environment where the privacy of the user matters the most.

In contrast to EduCash, the application focuses on security measures specifically to ensure the remittance security with the use of a payment gateway. User authentication to unsure that only users have access to the application. SSL encryption to encrypt the data that are sent into the application. EduCash also implements PCI compliance to prevent misuse of credit card, debit and cash transactions.

1.2.4 Donor Portal

This criterion refers to the functionalities that allows the donors to manage contributions of the users and track them effectively. This feature also donors to

review to manage personal information of users, and gain visibility into how the contribution of the user is utilized by the system. Give Lively implements a donor portal as a management tool for the donors. It is a feature where the donors and fundraisers of Give Lively navigates and provide them the access to user donation history, do users account details, make edits to users account, update users name, email address and password. Additionally, donor portal from give lively provides the donors and fundraisers the lists of continuous donations of users. Donors are also able to download donor data in a form of CSV files. As for Donorbox, the feature allows the donors to access the receipts of user donations, allows the donors to manage repeated donations, and allows them to manage user profiles. GoFundMe on the other hand, provides a donor portal where users are able to create profiles, track donations, and receive campaign updates, allowed donors to stay informed about the impact of user contributions, enhanced transparency and engagement on the application.

In contrast, EduCash implements a donor portal as a profile feature for donors where users are able to donate to scholarship agencies. Then the agencies disbursed the funds to the students who are catered by the application. Donors are also able to access users donation history which are generated receipts that includes users name, the amount donated and the scholarship agencies where donors sent users donation, and the date and time the donation is performed. Additionally, then are able to download the receipt that is generated by the application using the receipts that are sent based on the payment gateway used.

1.3 Project Scope

EduCash is a web-based application that aimed to financially assist college students that are underprivileged but qualified to benefit from the said financial assistance, through donation from NGO and other specific individuals who are eager to donate. EduCash only caters to college students that are currently academically based in Bacolod City. The following subsequent sections are the discussion that defines the project scope to identify the project requirements.

1.3.1 Educational Institutions

The application focuses only on any institutions that provides undergraduate programs located in Bacolod City. It is a home to a number of universities, and colleges. Many students tend to face financial problems that are considered to be a hindrance to the ability to complete their education. The application primarily focuses on directing financial aid to those students from the educational institutions located in Bacolod City that are in need, that helps in bridging the gap between resources that are available and financial constraints.

1.3.2 Target Users

Although the application primarily focuses on Bacolod City, it is not limited to students that resides within the city. It also supports underprivileged yet academically qualified students from other areas, as long as students are academically based in Bacolod City. The main target users include NGOs, private/government agencies, and individual donors who provide financial assistance to qualified recipients. Other users, such as banks and scholarship agencies, are discussed in the sub-sections followed.

1.3.2.1 Students

The primary users of the application are the students, or in the terminology adopted for this paper, Underprivileged and qualified college students academically based in Bacolod City, nonetheless of user residency. The application targets the students that often face financial problems, such as allowance, school materials, and even tuition fees. The application prioritizes only those students who illustrate academic excellence and financial need. The application monitors the academic performance of the students to ensure that only those who deserves it continue to receive financial aid and motivate the students to participate and continue to excel in academic performance.

1.3.2.2 Scholarship Agencies

Through the application, scholarship agencies are able to provide the students an application forms and manage the application process of the students efficiently. The application enables these agencies to review student profiles and user academic performances and efficiently select students for further process or officially consider them as applicant once matched. In addition, scholarship agencies received the money to be disbursed to the students, and the application provides the calculation of how the fund is distributed.

1.3.2.3 Donor

Private/Government agencies, NGO and other specific individuals eager to support the cause are the foundation of the application. Donors provide the monetary resources that are necessary to support user recipients. The application allows them to track user donation history, understand the impact of user unselfishness.

1.3.3 Donations

The application only accepts donations in a monetary form to make certain of efficient support for the recipients. EduCash only focuses on financial contributions that allows the donors to provide targeted assistance that directly alleviates the educational expenses of the students. The focus of monetary donations is to strengthen the application impact by offered a tangible resource for the recipients or students in need.

1.3.4 Student Requirements

The application aims only to support the students that genuinely excel in academic performances. To ensure this, the application provides a set eligibility criteria for the applicants in the system. These criteria aim to verify that the students are qualified, and qualified to be part of the cause, and ensures that students are in need of financial assistance. The criteria for qualification focus on the performance of the students in school and meet a certain financial condition to ensure that the donations are distributed to

support the students that are serious about user education and also creates a motivation for the students to maintain users progress academically.

EduCash is a centered application that is designed to aid the financial gap encountered by poor but qualified college students in Bacolod City. By technology-facilitated matching of donors, NGOs, and scholarship agencies with students, EduCash fosters a culture of philanthropy and social solidarity, in harmony with the vision of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) for inclusive and equitable quality education. Unlike other generic donation applications, EduCash offers an accessible and transparent application that guarantees endowments for qualified individuals and is therefore accountable and honest. With cash disbursements gone through various verifications, data validation, and security measures, it ensures the smoothest and safest way to transact, consequently safeguarded confidence of every stakeholder. Besides this, the immediate matching in scholarships provides for optimal resource allocation, thereby ensured that successful educational achievers are not held back because of cash constraints. EduCash not only closes the void in education but also gives students a chance to realize users dreams with a higher emphasis on social growth and development. An integrated and user-friendly website, EduCash is determined to set standards in educational philanthropy; EduCash makes certain that a better future does not allow financial restrictions on academic ambitions. This capstone project is testament to the possibility of technology as a catalyzed guarantee treat system-level solutions to dilemmas, ensured that technology paves a way for long-term social change.

CHAPTER II

SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS

This chapter discusses the general features of the project, as mentioned in the previous chapter. The application provides donors such as NGO and other specific individuals, and recipients which are the underprivileged and qualified college students a way to connect easily with each other, and to provide a fast inquiries and initial screen for scholarships. The project team aims to support college students by the provision of financial support through donations with the use of the application. The sections that followed introduce the features that helped the application to reach its goals and objectives.

2.1 System Perspective and General Perspective

The five general features of the system are illustrated in the Figure 1 namely Allowance Distribution, Donor Portal, Scholarship Match, Data Analytics, and Document Verification. By the components presented, components that work together to form the performance process of the application, the project team planned and reviewed the specification to make sure that the development and initiation of the application is successful. Each feature is designed to focus on connection of a smooth transaction in the application, The project team aims to seamlessly integrate these features to guarantee a user-friendly and an efficient application for donors and recipients. The development process involves detailed plan and repetitive test to make sure that each feature meet the needs of users effectively. As shown in the sections followed and its subsequent sections

in this chapter discusses the assumptions and dependencies, understand comprehensively and analysis of the project facilitated its development.

Figure 1. EduCash General Features

2.1.1 Donor Portal

This feature provided donors a way to contribute monetarily to support the goals of the project through payment integrations of bank system as one time or repeated donors on the scholarship agencies to support. Donors are also able to donate through payment gateways that is integrated in the application such as

PayPal, Gcash, and Maya. Individual donors have the decision to keep themselves as anonymous donors for those who value privacy and does not want to be acknowledged. This feature also provides the donors the proof of user donation through acknowledgement receipt that is generated by the application. The acknowledgement receipt includes the purpose of user transaction which is to donate. The receipt provides the donor a view of user transaction such as the amount of user donation, on what agency the donor has donated and the time and date of the transaction.

2.1.2 Scholarship Match

This feature provided the students smooth and faster inquiries of scholarships existed that cater to students that are academically based in Bacolod city, users are able to provide information necessary to apply for a scholarship included users credentials and performance at school. After which, the system is able to provide them the scholarship agency on which users credentials are matched. This feature also assists scholarship agencies to find applicants that are qualified students who meet user criteria and user specific requirements. The requirements that are set by the scholarship agencies in the application that the students fill out, serve only as a screening process and not a direct way that the students be considered as an official applicant of user program, only the approval for further transactions are sent to students as a notification.

2.1.2.1 Postings

When used by a scholarship agency, this feature allows that agency to post announcements in the application that are viewable in the interface

of the students. Among other matters, this means that the agency may inform the student of certain procedures or applications that are need for the application for such a scholarship. The application period is also stated, along with contact information and frequently asked questions, all with the intent to provide to better understand in the end of the student. When the scholarship agency feels that an announcement is complete and no longer necessary, that announcement is archived. Ability to archive also allows the management of the interface so that no superfluous announcements are shown to the student. An archive feature allows the agency to revisit any announcement when in need of information, as republished are fastened and the scholarship-related information are easily tracked.

2.1.3 Data Analytics

The data analytics feature displayed in a dashboard consists of the data such as total amount of donations gathered, total number of applicants, total number of NGO donors, which are represented in a bar graph, and a pie chart of the percentage of the individual and anonymous donors. This feature serves as a significant element for evaluation of the performance of the application. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the application. Specifically, the application provides an analyzation and display key metrics that are discussed further in this section of the paper.

2.1.3.1 Total Amount of Donations Report

The application collects and displays the total amount that are gathered from donors. These data are able to provide a point of reference

for measurement of the fundraising efficiency of the application and to identify the patterns that operates donor contributions. As amounts are monitored, these serve as substantial indicators of the impact of encouragement in educational support of the application.

2.1.3.2 Donors Pie Chart

The distinction between the specific NGOs, private/government agencies, individuals, and anonymous donors allowed the application to efficiently supply assorted preferences and motive of the donors. Anonymous donors, contrarily, highlighted the significance of privacy and discretion in donation. As for the specific individuals who want to seek acknowledgement for users contributions. The application only shows the percentage of and specific individuals, NGOs, private/government agencies, and anonymous donors in a pie chart.

2.1.4 Allowance Distribution

In this feature, the students are able to claim financial aid calculated by the application through payment gateways integrated in the application. The distribution is scheduled on a specific month each semester and each time before the distribution, students must submit the reports of their academic performance. Students must maintain their academic performance as based in the eligibility criteria to avoid being classified dropped as an applicant of the scholarship agency. When the general average fall below the criteria set by the scholarship agency, this allows them to disqualify the applicant to avail the provisions from the scholarship agencies and the

student is not able to match with the scholarship agency for the next period of disbursement until criteria is matched again.

2.1.5 Document Verification

This arguably becomes one of the great features incorporated into the application to sustain the originality and authenticity of the submission of the users. It is the defense that protects the integrity of the application against schemes such as fraudulent submissions and misrepresentation. This set of operations protects the integrity of the identity of the applicants and other assertions in more thorough verification to prove that he or she is an ethically and legitimately acceptable candidate for the benefited service. It validates uploads from supported documents, academic records, financial statements, and identity proofs through stringent loopholes verification. The system further minimizes errors for it to check every document against a reliable database while engaged in good security services aimed at caught attempts of crashes and forgeries. With this feature, the application builds confidence in scholarship agencies to put users trust and aid the qualified and well-qualified students.

2.2 Operating Environment

This web-based application supplicates funds from donors, specifically the NGO and other specific individuals who are eager to help in such a cause, enabled students to earn financial support that accords to user academic performance, to ensure increased motivation and engagement in user studies. To ensure a successful development phase, it is essential to identify the hardware and software specifications that supports these tools.

This section outlines the requirements for the development and implementation of this project.

2.2.1 Hardware Recommendations

The hardware requirements for development have been efficiently selected to guarantee optimal performance throughout the entire project with the least amount of time wasted. The perhaps most distinguished member of this list is the AMD Ryzen 5 [WWW12], one of the fastest processors there is today, known for its speed and multitask potential. Such a CPU possesses immense power and efficiency to conduct functions like code compilation, administrated demand algorithms and debug tests, all while running the development workstation in the SAF environment. Its multi-core architecture, therefore, gives the much-needed capability of performance demand in resource applications, such as backend processes and online media applications, without to consume processed resources, thus promoted productivity by reduction of lag. To complement the process power, 8 GB of DDR4 RAM is included, which is just right for reliable memory support. This means developers are able to open multiple applications-such as IDEs, version control systems, virtual machines, and browsers for testing-at the same time and with enjoyable performance. The project team effortlessly drift into the code to be debugged and continue to be tested. Secondary storage that ranged from 256 GB to 512 GB SSD, provision to a broadened range of responsiveness. An SSD reduces the time taken to start up files and applications, and thus boots faster, reads and writes faster, and ultimately maximizes user experience. More useful in the phase

of compilation and deployment since data and resource access is needed with extraordinary rapidity there.

Component	Development
Processor	AMD Ryzen 5
RAM	8 GB DDR4
Secondary Storage	256GB to 512GB SSD

Table 2. Hardware Recommendations.

2.2.2 Software Requirements

Table 3 illustrated the key software tools that are implemented that built the application and the collaboration processes involved. Integrated Environment: Visual Studio Code [WWW13] provides an Integrated IDE that has highly flexible and lightweight functionality in regard to the development and fix bugs. Git/GitHub [WWW15] are used for version control management in order to keep project files secure and provide team collaboration capabilities. PowerShell acts as an automation and system maintenance scripting terminal for the project team. For front-end development, the project team intends to use Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and Bootstrap 5 alongside JavaScript for an interactive user interface. PHP is utilized to aid in the back-end development. MySQL is used for management in the back-end database. The application is deployed on the Windows 10 or higher workstation. Three modes of communication within the project team are utilized: Microsoft Teams, Discord, and Google. These modes allow complete interaction among members of the project

team, plan sensitively, real-time coordination, and documentation. All these software requirements create a complete and well-structured development environment to ensure a successful implementation. The project team created the prototype used Figma. Such a strategic approach ensures that the application is flexible enough for any broad scope and permissible for future scale. PHP Mailer is used to send emails, and Tesseract OCR for document reading and validation.

Component	Software Tool
Integrated Development Environment (IDE)	Visual Code Studio
Version Control	Git/GitHub
Terminals	Power shell
Frontend Development	Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)/ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)/ JavaScript
Backend Development	PHP, MySQL
Operating System	Windows 10/11
Communication Applications	Microsoft Teams/ Discord
Collaboration Applications	Google Docs
Search Engine	Google Chrome
Prototyping	Figma
Frameworks and Libraries	BOOTSTRAP 5, jQuery
Engines	Tesseract OCR, PHP Mailer

Table 3. Software Recommendations

2.2.3 Connectivity Requirements

The project requires a stable internet connection and a web browser. An internet connection is essential to ensure smooth integration and uninterrupted operation, allowing online services such as web hosting is to be accessed and used with the system. An average speed of 25 Mbps helps ensure that the web application operates efficiently, with faster data transfer contributing to improved user experience and accessibility. However, if the internet speed drops below the specified threshold, problems such as slow downloads and increased latency may occur, which is able to negatively impact the overall user experience.

2.3 Design and Implementation Constraints.

In the implementation of this web-based application, there are no such systems that are able to do any act without boundaries. In systems development, constraints and difficulties are commonly encountered, such as user interface design. This section discusses the areas of concern in the development of the application.

2.3.1 Account Creation and Management.

The process starts when users try to log in. If the users do not have a registered account yet, users are required to do so. Upon sign up an account, users are able choose on the roles that existed in the application. For students options of being a recipient or a donor is possible. As for donors, these user types are categorized as individuals, Private/Government Agencies, or NGO. As for the donor type of individuals, one option is that the individual donors are able to hide their personal identity by being an anonymous donor.

2.3.2 Calculation for Distribution

This feature to calculate the distribution of money to the students is one of the fundamental functions of the application, the application provides the scholarship agencies a calculation of how to distribute the money to the students. It starts with the calculation of the top 20% of the total number of scholars in each scholarship agency. This group receives 60% of the total amount of the donation that has been gathered and divided accordingly. The remaining 80% of the scholars receives 40% of the total amount that has been collected. It is then followed by the same calculations but for top 30% of the total number of the students in the agency. Other method is to divide it to top 10 students or top 20 students and disregard the others. Alternatively, the agencies are able to equally divide the amount to all students.

Calculation	Number of Students	Formula of Distribution
Method 1	Top 20% Priority	60/40 Percent
Method 2	Top 30% Priority	60/40 Percent
Method 3	Top 10 only	Divided Equally
Method 4	Top 20 only	Divided Equally
Method 5	All scholars	Divided Equally

Table 4. Calculation Methods.

2.3.3 Matching Algorithm

The purpose of this is to develop a well-organized and dependable mechanism of matching student credentials to available scholarships matching user qualifications and needs. In this way, the application search for scholarships

be seamless, and it assures that qualified student profiles get matched with relevant sources of funds. Eligibility criteria are defined by the scholarship agencies, and the system use these parameters to accurately match the students. The matching of criteria is defined by student academic requirements like general weighted average of the student. Another requirement is user financial requirements, user demographics, and user special qualifications. Scholarship agencies are also able to set the deadline of the matching phase, when the current date is already past the deadline set by the scholarship agency, they are no more visible to the students.

2.3.4 Color-coded Interface

To consolidate some portions of the user interface, the project team decided to implement a color-coded scheme for each account type, ensuring consistency and minimizing potential confusion in navigating the system. The use of distinct background colors allows users to quickly identify their account type and enhances the overall usability of the application. For the student account, the background color is set to white, symbolizing simplicity and clarity, while for the donors, the interface adopts a subtle shade of blue, representing trust and reliability. In contrast, the scholarship agency accounts are assigned a subtle green background, signifying growth and opportunity. Despite these differences, there is a shared section of the UI accessible to all account type which is the dashboard within the reports interface. To maintain uniformity, the background color in this section is subtle red, chosen to emphasize the importance of the data presented. Meanwhile, the admin interface features a black background, providing a strong, authoritative design that distinguishes it from the other account types. This structured approach

to interface design not only reinforces user identity within the system but also contributes to an intuitive and user-friendly experience across the application.

Interface/Account Type	Background Color
Admin Account	Black
Student Account	White
Donor Account	Light Blue
Scholarship Agency Account	Light Green
Reports Interface	Light Yellow

Table 5. Color-Coded Interface.

2.4 Assumptions and Dependencies

This section of the paper covers conditions and factors required for the successful development, deployment, and operation of the application. It identifies some of the important expectations and outside influences that could have an effect on project implementation and maintenance. Such factors are very important to identify for risk management purposes and ensured alignment with the goals of the project.

2.4.1 Assumptions

These are beliefs and forecast variables that direct project development and implementation. Assumptions form a structure for it to understand the intended future position of systems under defined criteria and explain resources. Explicitly stated are the assumptions identified for user importance and implications for the application. These are important to set the project scope and limits, hence facilitated all stakeholders to develop a common unit of expectation. Stated in these assumptions clears ground to that accords to plan for all possible risks and

challenges. In addition, these provides a good basis to make decisions throughout development that concerned with the design choices and allocation of resources. User identification and validation play a key role in the sustainability of the life of the application. Further, these put one on access and normalize the development process, thereby positively influenced the degree of project success.

2.4.1.1 Financially Assist the Recipients.

One of the major assumptions of the application ensures that it targets group of students in serious financial needs while maintained excellent academic standards recognized. The focus of the application to aid qualified college students, fosters to maintain accountability and transparency since it only targets students that are qualified to receive the financial support. The application provides a concentrated impact and an efficient evaluation by to concentrate only in students that are academically based in Bacolod City.

2.4.1.2 Eager Donors to use Payment Gateways.

This assumption is grounded in the growth trend of digital payment adoption. The application provides an array of payment options that included PayPal, Gcash, and Maya, improved its accessibility and donor experience. This assumption supports the general adoption of digital wallets and traditional bank services, increased donation opportunities. It mitigates the barriers for donors who prefer specific payment gateways over others. Maintained security financial transactions across multiple payment gateways requires technical safeguards.

2.4.1.3 Retention Policy for Student Academic Standard.

This assumption incentivizes academic performance and aligns in distribution of financial support with the principles of excellence. The application monitors the students that are consistent with users academic performance to avoid to be classified as dropped in the application and continue received the support the students deserve. This is to make sure that the monetary donations are received by students who are genuinely committed to user education. This motivates the student applicants or scholars to actively engage with the application and user academics. A note of termination is given to the student that the credentials did not reach the criteria of eligibility to continue receive the financial support. However, students are still able to look for a scholarship agency that best match their academic eligibility and financial status.

2.4.2 Dependencies

these refers to criteria, systems or elements that are required externally for the success of the development, implementation, and operation of the project. These influences the functionality of the application and to make sure that the objectives are met productively. EduCash depends on partnerships, technological assets that are essential for absolute between donors and recipients. Below discusses the dependencies that are critical for reduction and mitigation of risks and to make sure that the alignment of the project with the needs of the user and expectations.

2.4.2.1 Security Measures

The application heavily relies on robust security measures to protect sensitive data as it is transmitted between servers, ensured the integrity and privacy of financial transactions and user information. To safeguard student accounts, the application implements Two-Factor Authentication (2FA), added an extra layer of security that required users to verify user identity through a secondary method. The use of SSL encryption ensures that all data transmitted is securely encrypted, prevented unauthorized access in the time of transfer. By to adhere to PCI Compliance standards, the application ensures that payment and credit card information is handled with the highest level of security, reduced risks associated with financial fraud.

The chapter outlined the guidelines for the process of system specifications of EduCash, a web-based application crafted for the provision of grants by the selection of various scholarships from the assessments of needful students. A balance of financial needs and education availability through the donor portal, scholarship matching, analytics of the data, distribution of allowances, and the verification of documents. The donor portal lets users create accounts, browse student profiles, and contribute anonymously or in the public eye while also keep track of transaction history and the production of receipts to maintain transparency. Scholarship matching uses powerful algorithms for matching qualified students who need support with relevant grants based on academic performance and financial assessments. Data analytics provide insights on donor tendencies, scholarship distributions, and how students perform, allowed administrators to optimize and enforce

The chapter outlines the guidelines for the process of system specifications of EduCash, a web-based application crafted for the provision of grants by the selection various scholarships from the assessments of needful students. A balance of financial needs and education availability through the donor portal, scholarship matching, analytics of the data, distribution of allowances, and the verification of documents. The donor portal lets users create accounts, browse student profiles, and contribute anonymously or in the public eye while also keep track of transaction history and the production of receipts to maintain transparency. Scholarship matching uses powerful algorithms for matching qualified students who need support with relevant grants based on academic performance and financial assessments. Document verification serves as a control mechanism that validates academic credentials, financial records, and identity submissions to preserve system credibility. Allowance distribution operates under predefined rules that support fair and timely release of financial assistance based on eligibility status and approved calculations. These components collectively establish operational consistency across the platform and reinforce accountability among all participating entities. Through structured specifications and integrated features, EduCash maintains an organized, transparent, and efficient framework for managing educational grant processes.

CHAPTER III

SYSTEM FEATURES

This chapter outlines the features of the application, which is intended to foster smooth interaction between scholarship agencies, donors, and students, are described in this chapter. Every module and feature support the goals of the system, improved efficiency and teamwork. Students in need are able to apply for scholarships with greater ease due to the system that streamlined the application and financed procedures. Activity diagrams and functional requirements illustrate the processes, highlighted key user actions and correspond system responses are discussed in the following sections.

3.1 System Decomposition

Each module is designed to streamline specific functions of the application, create a unified application that bridges the gap between qualified students and compassionate donors. Together, these modules ensure that the application is user-friendly, transparent, and impactful. The decomposition chart of the application highlights four essential modules that ensure its functionality and user-friendly design. First the account creation and management module, allows the user to have a centralized and a personalized space in the application. This module enables users to sign in, sign up, or edit users user information regardless of their role. Second is the scholarship matching module, where students are matched with the scholarship agencies that is suitable and accords to academic credentials. Third is the financial transactions module, it handles all the transactions of the users that includes money and provides method of calculation for disbursements. For instance, this

module allows donors to donate through payment gateways. And lastly, dashboard module provides all the users a data analytic report in the application. This module also includes the admin dashboard, where the admin is able to monitor scholarship agencies to verify the account registration and handling documents.

Figure 2. EduCash Decomposition Chart.

3.2 System Functionalities

In this section of the chapter, the project team provided details about the information of each module within the application. The subsequent sections presented an outline of how these functionalities are utilized during the interactions of the users, the corresponding system responses, and the underlying backend integration. The project team employed activity diagrams to illustrate the workflow of each module. These diagrams served as a visual representation of the behavior of the system, enhancing the

understanding of the logical sequence of actions and improving overall quality of the design of the application.

3.2.1 Account Creation and Management

The account creation and management module is the most important feature in the of the application. This function of the application provided all types of users a secure and a personalized space for improved user experience. This module allowed the users to sign up for a new account for new users logging in to registered account. This functionality also allowed the users to edit some personal information, such as email addresses, contact numbers, and passwords. This also comes with an email verification for more security and integrity in the application

3.2.1.1 Description and Priority

The account creation and management module is designed to handle all account registration, log in, and modification which is the first thing all users are required to do. regardless of the role of the user, all users follow the same functionality with different forms to fill out personal information and necessary documents that are required for validation and verification. The users are able to choose from three different account types namely the student, the donor, and the scholarship agency account. The application is able to recognize the account type and save the data in the database. The application then retrieves the credentials when the user logs in to their account and heads the users to a specific user interface based on their account type.

3.2.1.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned on the previous main section, the account creation and management module provided the users a centralized space for all account types. And users have the option to choose from different roles such as student, donor, and scholarship agency. As for the scholarship agency, before having access to the features of the application, the admin monitors the scholarship agency accounts and provides a message for further verification of the account. This functionality is further discussed in the following sections of this chapter. And once logged in the application checks the account type of the user so that the users are headed to its respective user interface, the activity diagram below provided a visual representation of the flow of the sign up, log in, and modifying of the user data. The flow starts when the user chooses to register or log in to an existing account. Upon registration, the user is required to input or to fill out necessary information such as email address, name, contact information, and password. The application then sends a verification token to the email address provided by the user. Once the email has been verified, the user is now able to log in and have access to the application features. The user is also able to edit user data once logged in. However, logging in to an account that is not verified through email results to a prompted error message using jQuery stating that the email is not yet verified.

Function Name	Account Creation and Management
Function Description	This function allowed the users to create, log in, and edit other personal information.
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Upon registration, users are requested to choose an account type ○ Upon log in, users must have a verified account. ○ Upon modifying personal data, users must log in to an account.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The user is now able to access the features of the application.
Activity Flow	
User	EduCash
<pre> graph TD subgraph User Start(()) --> Register{Register an account?} Register -- yes --> SignUp[Sign up] SignUp --> InputInfo[Input personal Information] InputInfo --> LogIn[Log in] Register -- no --> Start end subgraph EduCash SendEmail[Send email verification] --> InputCode[Input Verification Code] InputCode -- Valid? --> Valid{Valid?} Valid -- No --> Error1[prompt error message] Error1 --> Register Valid -- yes --> SaveData[Save user data] SaveData --> End(()) LogIn --> InputCred[Input Credentials] InputCred --> CredValid{Credentials valid?} CredValid -- No --> Error2[prompt error message] Error2 --> Register CredValid -- yes --> UserLoggedIn[user logged in] UserLoggedIn --> End end SignUp --> SendEmail InputInfo --> SendEmail LogIn --> InputCred </pre>	
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ On the registration interface, a button is visible that allows the user to head back to the log in interface.
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ User inputs invalid credentials or a non-verified account results to a prompted error message.

Table 6. Account Creation and Management Activity Diagram.

3.2.1.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the task needed to utilize the functionality of the account creation and management feature. Given two options, if the user does not have an existing account, three buttons are available to click based on the desired account type. Or if the user already has an account, a log in form is directly displayed after the splash page of the application where students are able to input the credentials that matches against the database.

- a. The log in form is displayed in the right-hand side and is beside the logo of the application.
- b. Inputting the credentials in the log in form heads the user to the profile page if credentials are matched and valid.
- c. If the user is not verified through email, an error message is prompted.
- d. Three buttons are displayed under the log in form for account registration.
- e. Clicking the button results to different registration forms.
- f. After a successful registration a token for verification is sent to the given email address.
- g. The email provides a link to the application.
- h. Invalid tokens result to a prompted error message.
- i. If the account is a scholarship agency, the admin is notified.
- j. The admin is then able to verify the scholarship agency

3.2.2 Scholarship Matching

The scholarship matching module is an essential feature of the application followed by the account creation and management module. This functionality benefits the two users of the application namely the students and the scholarship agencies. This feature allows the scholarship agencies to post information and procedures for scholarship applications and set criteria for students to match.

3.2.2.1 Description and Priority

This scholarship matching feature requires criteria for the scholarship agencies to be set and requires documents for students to upload. This feature also includes postings which allows the agencies to provide students information about their program. The students are able to scroll through their feed where scholarship information is provided.

3.2.2.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned in the main section, this feature allows the students to match for a scholarship agency based on the qualifications and the set eligibility criteria or scroll through postings of the scholarship agency. Illustrated in table 7, is the visualization of the flow of the feature. For students, it starts by checking if the documents are updated or valid. As for the scholarship agency, criteria are required to be set for them to be visible when the students are looking for a match. When a match is found, the students are able to click the apply button and is redirected to an application form. The scholarship agencies are then notified if a student sent an application.

Function Name	Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Function Description	This function allows the scholarship agencies to post scholarship, set criteria, and manage applicants.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The account requires to be a student or a scholarship agency account. ○ Documents must be validated, and criteria is required to be set. 	
Post condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Students are now accepted/rejected for the scholarship. 	
Activity Flow		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scholarship agencies are able to navigate through postings or to the interface where criteria are set. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Users are prompted if documents are invalid or missing. 	

Table 7. Scholarship Matching and Postings Activity Diagram.

3.2.2.3 Functional Requirements.

The project team outlined the tasks that are needed to utilize the functionality of the scholarship matching and postings feature. The scholarship agencies set the criteria for matching, and the students are matched based on the eligibility in the academic performance. The scholarship matching feature is accessible the navbar menu “criteria” for the scholarship agencies, and “scholarship” for the student. However, the postings feature is accessible in the navbar menu “feed” for the students, and navbar menu “post” for the scholarship agencies.

- a. The students click on “Feed” on the navbar.
- b. The posts from scholarship agencies are displayed.
- c. Students are provided with the information and procedures for application.
- d. The scholarship agencies click on “Post”, and the form are displayed.
- e. Scholarship agencies are able to provide the information and procedures for application.
- f. For matching, the scholarship agencies click on “criteria”, and a form are displayed.
- g. Students click on “Scholarships”, and a match appears.
- h. If the student has invalid or missing documents, an error message appears.
- i. Scholarship agencies are required to set criteria for matching.
- j. If the scholarship agency is not yet verified by the admin, the feature is inaccessible, and an error prompt appears.

3.2.3 Financial Transactions

The financial transactions module is composed of two major functionality such as donation and allowance distribution. allowance distribution also includes one functionality of this module which is the calculation that is discussed further in the previous chapter. The donate feature is accessible to the users with donor accounts. While the allowance distribution feature is accessible to the users with scholarship agency account.

3.2.3.1 Description and Priority

The financial transaction is the core of the functionality and purpose of the implementation of this application. This feature allows the donors to donate to a scholarship agency with a given criteria such as the location and the minimum average required in that scholarship agencies. The scholarship agencies then uses that donation to disburse to the scholars using payment gateways according to the method of calculation that is set by that scholarship agency.

3.2.3.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

As mentioned in the previous subsequent section, this feature handles all the financial transactions in the application from sending donations to scholarship agencies, allowance distributions to the students, and selecting calculation methods. Illustrated in Table 8 and 9 are the visualization of the flow of the process in the financial transactions of the application. The process of the donation feature starts when the donor navigates to the donate button in the navbar menu. After clicking the button,

a form appears with two dropdown inputs. The donor then is able to input criteria such as the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement for student eligibility. After the donor has submitted the form, scholarship agencies that matches the criteria appears in a tabular format. If there are no scholarship agencies found, an error message is prompted. Another flow aside from donate is to view the scholars of that scholarship agencies. Upon clicking on the donate button, the donor is then headed to the interface where payment methods are displayed. After a successful transaction, the donor is requested to upload the receipt of the donation to inform the scholar agency that such transactions happened. As for the scholarship agency, after receiving the donation, the donors are displayed in the inbox section of the scholarship agency alongside with the payment method, amount, and date of donation. Scholarship agencies are able to acknowledge the donation to inform the donor that the transaction went through, and that the money is received by the scholarship agency .When the time comes for the scholarship agency to disburse the money, a method of calculation is set first, and the disbursement of the amount is based on the calculation method that is set by the scholarship agency. The students are also able to notify that the allowance distribution has been received through email and clicking the acknowledgement button by navigating into the inbox section where the allowance distribution history is located.

Function Name	Donate	
Function Description	This feature allows the donors to donate to scholarship agencies.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The account requires to be a donor account. ○ Scholarship agencies are required to upload QR code. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Donors successfully donated to scholarship agencies. ○ Scholarship Agencies receive a receipt to acknowledge. 	
Activity Flow		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aside from donating, the donors are able to view the scholars of the scholarship agency. ○ A button is visible on top to go back to the previous page. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ An error prompt appears when there are no agencies found. 	

Table 8. Donate Activity Diagram

Function Name	Allowance Distribution	
Function Description	This feature allows the scholarship agencies to disburse money to students.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The account requires to be a scholarship agency account. ○ Students are required to upload QR code. ○ Before disbursement, scholarship agencies select a method of calculation. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scholarship agencies successfully disbursed money to students. ○ Students received the remittance. 	
Activity Flow		
Scholarship Agency	EduCash	Students
<pre> graph TD Start(()) --> S1[Select a calculation method] S1 --> E1[provide list of students with the amount to be distributed based on calculation] E1 --> S2[Click the disburse icon] S2 --> E2[Select a payment gateway] E2 --> S3[upload receipt] S3 --> E3[save disbursement history] E3 --> S4[allowance received] S4 --> E4[acknowledge receipt] E4 --> S5[email sent for acknowledgement] S5 --> End(()) </pre>	<pre> graph TD Start(()) --> S1[provide list of students with the amount to be distributed based on calculation] S1 --> S2[Click the disburse icon] S2 --> S3[Select a payment gateway] S3 --> S4[upload receipt] S4 --> S5[save disbursement history] S5 --> S6[allowance received] S6 --> S7[acknowledge receipt] S7 --> S8[email sent for acknowledgement] S8 --> End(()) </pre>	<pre> graph TD Start(()) --> S1[allowance received] S1 --> S2[acknowledge receipt] S2 --> End(()) </pre>
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aside from donating, the donors are able to view the scholars of the scholarship agency. ○ A button is visible on top to go back to the previous page. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ An error prompt appears when there are no agencies found. 	

Table 9. Allowance Distribution Activity Diagram

3.2.3.3 Functional Requirements.

The project team outlined the tasks that are needed to utilize the functionality of the financial transactions feature. The donate process is accessible for the donors in the navbar menu “Donate” and a form appears for the donors to input criteria such as location and the minimum average requirement for the scholarship agencies. The allowance distribution process is accessible to scholarship agencies navbar menu “disbursement”.

- a. The donors click “Donate” in the navbar and are headed to input a form.
- b. The donors input the location and minimum average requirement of the scholarship agency.
- c. An error message is prompted when there are no scholarship agencies found.
- d. The donors click the view button on the “actions” column, and a list of scholars are displayed.
- e. Donors click the donate button and select a payment gateway.
- f. Donors upload the receipt as proof of donation.
- g. The scholarship agencies received the donation.
- h. An email is sent to the scholarship agencies after a successful donation from donors.
- i. The scholarship agencies click on the inbox menu in the sidebar.
- j. The list of donors who donated is displayed in a tabular format.
- k. The scholarship agencies click the eye icon in the “Receipt” column to view the receipt.

- l. The scholarship agencies click the thumbs up icon in the “Actions” column to acknowledge the receipt.
- m. An email is sent to the donor to notify that the scholarship agency has received the donation.
- n. After selecting a calculation method, the list of scholars is displayed in a tabular format and a disburse button appears.
- o. The students are sorted according to the average.
- p. The data displayed in the tabular format includes the average of the students, the amount to disbursed and the name of the students.
- q. When the scholarship agency clicks on the bank icon on the “Actions” column, the interface is redirected to where the payment methods appear.
- r. The scholarship agency selects a payment method.
- s. The QR Code of the students appear.
- t. The scholarship agency scans the QR code of the student.
- u. After a successful transaction, the scholarship agency is requested to upload the receipt of the transaction.
- v. The student received the allowance disbursed.
- w. The student clicks on the acknowledgement icon.
- x. An email is sent to the scholarship agency after student clicks on the acknowledgement.
- y. Transaction is saved in the transaction history of the scholarship agency,
- z. The student is now provided with the financial support based on the calculation selected.

3.2.4 Dashboard

The dashboard module is composed of two features, which is the scholarship monitoring in the admin dashboards, and the data analytics report. These data analytics reports are then displayed different data representation and is accessible for all the users in the application. This feature also allows the admin to monitor non-verified scholarship agencies and communicate through email using the application.

3.2.4.1 Description and Priority

The data analytics report provides the users with different data representation of reports in the application. However, this feature of the application requires user data to function to track the total amount of the donation, the number of students that are registered over time, and the comparison of each donor types. Additionally, the scholarship monitoring feature is only used and available for the admin. This is to ensure the legitimacy of the scholarship agency.

3.2.4.2 Stimulus/Response Sequences

Table 10 illustrates the process flow for the Scholarship Monitoring feature of the dashboard module. The process is initiated whenever a scholarship agency registers in the EduCash application. Upon registration, the scholarship agency is required to submit the necessary verification documents before gaining access to system functionalities. The administrator then reviews the submitted documents through the admin dashboard to assess the legitimacy of the scholarship agency. If the

submitted requirements are complete and valid, the administrator verifies the scholarship agency, allowing it to fully access the platform. In cases where the submitted documents are incomplete or missing, the system displays an error message, preventing verification until all requirements are

Function Name	Scholarship Monitoring	
Function Description	This function allows the admin to monitor non-verified scholarship agencies in the application.	
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To monitor scholarship agencies, the account must be an admin account. 	
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The admin has now verified the scholarship agency. 	
Activity Flow		
Admin	EduCash	Scholarship Agency
<pre> graph TD subgraph Admin Start(()) --> ShowList[show list of non-verified scholarship agency] ShowList --> VerifyUser[Verify the user] SendEmailAdmin[Send email to scholarship agency] end subgraph EduCash VerifyUser --> Decision{Missing/suspicious files?} Decision -- No --> Verified[Scholarship agency is verified] end subgraph ScholarshipAgency SendEmailAgency[Send email notification] End(()) end ShowList --> VerifyUser VerifyUser --> Decision Decision -- Yes --> SendEmailAdmin Verified --> SendEmailAgency SendEmailAgency --> End </pre>		
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A button is visible for the admin to view the data analytics report. 	
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admin verifies the scholarship agency while having missing files results to an error message. 	

Table 10. Scholarship Monitoring Activity Diagram

Table 11, on the other hand, presents the process flow of the Data Analytics Report feature. This process begins when a user clicks the Report button located on the sidebar of the application. Once activated, the system retrieves relevant data and displays it in various graphical and chart-based representations. These reports allow users to monitor donation transactions, user registrations, and other system-related statistics. The feature includes navigation controls that enable users to return to the previous page. However, in situations where the user experiences a slow or unstable internet connection, the data analytics reports may fail to load properly, resulting in delayed or unavailable visual outputs.

Function Name	Data Analytics Report
Function Description	This function allows the users to keep track of the transactions through different data representations.
Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any user types or account types are able to access the feature.
Post Condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The application provides the users graphs and charts of thr data analytics reports
Activity Flow	
User	EduCash
<pre> graph TD Start(()) --> Click[Click "Reports" Button] Click --> Pie[Display donor pie chart] Click --> Students[Display chart for number of students in monthly interval] Click --> Donations[Display line chart for total donations in monthly interval] Pie --> End((())) Students --> End Donations --> End </pre>	
Alternate Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users are provided with a button that heads back to the previous page
Exception Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow internet connection results to the data not being displayed.

Table 11. Data Analytics Report Activity Diagram

3.2.4.3 Functional Requirements

The project team outlined the processes needed to utilize the functionality of the dashboard module. Upon clicking on the reports section on the sidebar, the users are headed to the page where the data are displayed in different data representations such as graphs and charts. The users are able to track the total amount of donations in the application, the total number of students registered over time, and a comparison of different donor types. As for the scholarship agency monitoring feature exclusively for the admin, scholarship agencies are monitored in the admin dashboard. Every time a scholarship agency has registered, it appears in the admin dashboard as non-verified accounts. The admin has the power to view the documents submitted by the scholarship agencies. It is also possible for the admin to send an email to the scholarship agency using the application whenever the admin thinks that the documents submitted are suspicious or when there is something that needs to be clarified. Once the documents are validated by the admin, the scholarship agency is now fully verified and have access to the system features.

- a. User clicks on reports button in the sidebar.
- b. Data are displayed in the dashboard through graphs and charts.
- c. Click the button “Go back” to return to the previous page.
- d. Scholarship agency registers an account.
- e. Scholarship agency is now classified as non-verified.
- f. Scholarship agencies are displayed into the admin dashboard.

- g. The admin is able to view the submitted documents.
- h. If the admin tried to verify the agency while having no documents submitted, an error message is prompted.
- i. Admin is able to send email to the scholarship agency through the application.
- j. Admin is notified when a scholarship agency has uploaded new documents.

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the system features of the application, designed to enhance interaction between different account types such as students, donors, scholarship agencies, and the admin. The chapter introduces four major functionalities that supported the implementation and the development of the application. The project team provided a decomposition chart and activity diagrams to illustrate the major functions of the system. Flow charts or activity diagrams provided a visual illustration of the process flows of the system features such as the account creation and management, scholarship matching, financial transactions, and the dashboard module. Together with the flowcharts are the precondition, post condition, alternate flow, and the exception flow that handles the error and prompting error messages to provide quality and user-friendly interface that improved the user experience.

CHAPTER IV

EXTERNAL INTERFACE REQUIREMENTS

The external interface of the EduCash project encompasses several key components that enhanced the user experience and facilitated seamless interactions within the application. This chapter outlined the specifications and various user interfaces including the login page, reports dashboard, donation interfaces, matching interfaces, user profiles, and many more. Each of these interfaces played a major role in ensuring the satisfaction of users and efficient utilization of the EduCash project. By addressing these specific requirements and characteristics of these user interfaces, EduCash delivered a comprehensive and intuitive application for user access and provide educational and financial assistance to students in Bacolod City.

4.1 User Interfaces

The user interfaces of the EduCash application are the gateway through which donors, students, and scholarship agencies together with the admin interact with one another. The user interfaces encompass the interactive and visual elements that enabled the seamless access to features and navigation. This section of the chapter explores the principles, usability, and the layout that ensures an intuitive and engaging user experience. EduCash provided a color-coded interface depending on the user types to prevent confusion and by consolidating the background color to identify different account types such as donors, scholarship agencies, and students.

4.1.1 Login Page

Shown in Figure 3 is the Login Page of the EduCash application provided a user-friendly interface for a secure account access. Beside the logo, two input fields are provided where users to input email address and the password. A forgot password hyperlink is provided below if ever the user forgot his/her password. By clicking the log in button, users are redirected to user profile page and access the system features. however, if the user is not registered yet, three buttons are provided below that serve as the user account type and each button heads to different input fields.

The screenshot displays the login interface for the EduCash application. On the left side, there is a logo for EduCash, which includes a blue silhouette of a person wearing a graduation cap, a green dashed circular arrow, and a green Malaysian Ringgit symbol. Below the logo, the text "EduCash" is written in a blue and green font. On the right side, there is a light blue login form. The form contains the following elements: an "Email" label above a text input field with the placeholder "e.g example@gmail.com"; a "Password" label above a text input field with the placeholder "Enter your Password" and a toggle icon; a "Remember me" checkbox; a "Forgot password?" link; a black "Sign In" button; a "Don't have an account?" link; a "Register as" label; and three buttons labeled "Student", "Donor", and "Agency".

Figure 3. Login Interface.

4.1.2 Forgot Password

As shown in Figure 4 is the forgot password form interface of the EduCash application. If ever the user forgot his/her password, an input field for email is provided and the application sends an email of the 6-digit code for the verification of the user. After the user has entered the email address, by clicking the button heads to another page to continue the flow of the process. After redirecting, another input appears where the user is able to enter the 6-digit verification code.

The figure displays two sequential steps of the 'Forgot your password?' process. The first step shows an email input field and a 'Send reset code' button. The second step shows a confirmation message and a 6-digit code input field with a 'Verify code' button.

Figure 4. Forgot Password Interface

4.1.3 Student Registration Page

When the user decided to register as a student, the button named student is accessible at the bottom left side of the log in form. When clicked, the user then is redirected to the form where the user is able to input or to fill out the form to register a student account. The form includes the full name of the student, the school where the student is currently enrolled, the contact number of the student, the program of study, email address, date of birth, and the password confirmation. Upon clicking the continue button, the account is now processed for verification. A button is also accessible if the user already has an account and wants to head back to the log in form.

The screenshot displays a registration form titled "Create a Student Account". The form is organized into two columns of input fields. The left column contains fields for "Full Name", "Contact.", "Email", and "Password". The right column contains fields for "Search School", "Search Program", a date field labeled "mm/dd/yyyy" with a calendar icon, and "Confirm Password". Below the input fields, there is a large "Continue" button and a smaller button that says "Already have an account? Sign in". The entire form is enclosed in a light blue border.

Figure 5. Student Registration Interface.

4.1.4 Upload Credentials form

Once a student is already registered and has logged in to an existing student account, the student is then redirected to the form where necessary documents and files is uploaded and is validated by the application. The students are required to upload the certificate of enrolment, validated school ID, and the certified true copy of grades for the application to verify that the user is currently enrolled. To verify that the student is in need or underprivileged when it comes to the financial aspect, some documents are required to submit which is the certificate of indigency and the proof of income of the parents of the students. The application aims only to support the students that are underprivileged but is deserving and has commendable performance in education.

The screenshot displays a user interface titled "Upload Credentials". It features five distinct upload options arranged in two rows. Each option is represented by an icon and a text label. The first row includes: a graduation cap icon for "Upload certified true copy of grades", a document icon for "Upload certificate of enrolment", and a school ID card icon for "Upload validated school ID". The second row includes: a house with a heart icon for "Upload Certificate of Indigency" and a receipt icon for "Upload Proof of Income". At the bottom center of the interface is a prominent "Submit" button.

Figure 6. Upload Credentials Interface

4.1.5 Duplicate File Error

Upon submission of the documents submitted by the students, the application then validates and verifies the data. In instance where the student has uploaded a duplicate file, the application detects and provide the students a prompt error message. The prompted error message tells the students that the documents submitted has duplicate, and the student must select another file or document to upload. Clicking the OK button head backs the student to the form and the student is now able to continue uploading the files and documents for the application to process and validate.

Figure 7. Duplicate File Error Interface

4.1.6 Student Profile

After a successful submission of files and documents that are required, the application then validates and verifies that documents. The student is now able to access the application feature which is the scholarship matching feature. In the log in interface, it shown the name of the student, the personal information such as contact number, email address, and the monthly income of the parents of the student on the left side of the main content of the screen. On the right side, the academic information of the student is shown which is the school where the student is enrolled, the program of study of the student, and the average grade in the previous semester. There are two buttons accessible for the student, namely the update credentials button, and the edit profile button. The update credentials button heads to the form where students upload documents which is shown in Figure 6.

The screenshot displays a student profile interface for Kessel John Vingno. At the top, there is a circular profile picture of a student in a white t-shirt and shorts, standing outdoors. Below the photo are two buttons: "Update Photo" and "Submit". The student's name, "Kessel John Vingno", is centered below the photo. The profile is divided into two main sections: "Personal Information" and "Academic Information".

Personal Information	Academic Information
Email kessel@gmail.com	School University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)
Contact +639652632323	Program Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
Parent's Monthly Income 12,000.00	Average 94.63 %

At the bottom of the profile, there are two buttons: "Update Credentials" and "Edit Profile".

Figure 8. Student Profile Interface

4.1.7 Scholarship Feed

When the user clicks on the Feed section on the side navigation bar, the student is headed into the feed section where the information of the scholarship agencies are posted. The student is able to gather information about certain scholarships with the specific requirements and procedures for the application process. Shown in Figure 9 is the interface of the feed of postings from the scholarship agencies. It provides the name of the scholarship agency, the scholarship benefits, the eligibility and application requirements, and the deadline of submission together with the announcement date of the result and contact information.

Mcdo Agency

<h3 style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Scholarship Benefits</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Monthly Living Allowance ✓ Health and Wellness Support ✓ Employment Assistance After Graduation 	<h3 style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Eligibility Requirements</h3> <p>With Degree programs related to:</p> <p>✗ With minimum grade requirement of [90% - 95%]</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Application Requirements</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📄 Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records 📄 Certificate of Enrollment or Admission 📄 Copy of Valid School ID 📄 Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian 📄 Certificate of Indigency from Barangay/Municipality 	<h3 style="text-align: center; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Application Process</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚙️ register ⚙️ apply
<p>📅 Deadline of Submission: [2025-05-28]</p> <p>📅 Announcement of Result: [2025-06-07]</p>	
<p style="text-align: right;">For more inquiries, contact us as 📞 [+2147483647] or ✉️ [mcdo@gmail.com]</p>	

Figure 9. Feed Interface

4.1.7 Matched Scholarships

Upon clicking on the scholarship section on the side navigation bar, the student is redirected into the page where scholarships that matched with the credentials are displayed. As shown in Figure 10 are the scholarship agencies that matched with the qualifications and living conditions of the students. The interface also shows the deadline of application and the profile photo of the scholarship agency.

Figure 10. Matched Scholarships Interface

4.1.9 Application Form

After the student has clicked on the “apply now” button, the student is then redirected into the application form. As shown in Figure 11, is the application form where the students fill out and submit to the scholarship agency. The application form provides a question to the student of why is that student deserve the scholarship in a minimum of 200 words. To guide the students of the number of words that is currently being typed, a word counter below at the bottom right side of the text-area is provided. After the student reached a minimum of 200 words, a button at the bottom center is displayed and upon clicking the button, the application of the student is sent to the scholarship agency.

Why do you deserve this Scholarship? (Please write a minimum of 200 words)

I believe I deserve this scholarship because I am committed to achieving academic excellence while using my education to create meaningful impact in my community. Throughout my academic journey, I have consistently demonstrated dedication, perseverance, and a strong work ethic, even in the face of financial challenges. My passion for learning drives me to continuously improve myself, not only for personal success but also to contribute to the betterment of society.

Receiving this scholarship would greatly ease my financial burden, allowing me to focus more on my studies and participate in academic and community initiatives that foster growth and development. I plan to use my knowledge and skills to help address pressing issues in my community, such as improving access to education and creating opportunities for underprivileged youth.

This scholarship represents more than just financial assistance; it is an opportunity to further develop my potential, enhance my leadership abilities, and give back to those who have supported me along the way. I am determined to maximize this opportunity and uphold the values of hard work, responsibility, and service. With your support, I can continue striving toward my academic goals and become a positive force for change. Thank you and God Bless!

Words: 201

Submit Application

Figure 11. Application Essay Interface.

4.1.10 Student Inbox

When the student clicks on the inbox section in the side navigation bar, the student is headed where the notifications are being sent in the application. As shown in Figure 12 is the interface of the inbox of the student. In the interface, it shows the notification that the application sent by the student has been approved together with the disclaimer notice that the student is not an official scholar of the agency outside of the application. The interface also shows the financial transactions of the allowance distribution. The transaction shows the transaction id, and the message that the student has received the distribution together with the amount, the name of the agency, the payment gateway used. There are two buttons, the first one is the view button where the student is able to view the receipt, and the second one is the acknowledge button where the student is able to let the donor know that the money has been received.

Figure 12. Student Inbox Interface.

4.1.11 Student Files Section

When the student clicks on the credentials section on the navigation bar, the student then is redirected to the page where the files and documents that has been submitted are able to be accessed. As shown in Figure 13 is the interface of the credentials section page where uploaded files are located. In the interface, there are five documents that are shown namely the grades, the certificate of enrolment, the validated school ID, the certificate of indigency of the student, together with the tax exemption certificate. On the right side of the screen, a view action is provided to the student in which the files are accessed upon clicking the view icon.

Documents	Action

Figure13. Uploaded Files Interface.

4.1.12 Donor Registration Page

When the user decided to help scholarship agencies support students in financial aspects, the button at the bottom center of the login form shown in Figure 3 is accessible for creating a donor account. Upon clicking the button, the user then is redirected into the page where the registration form for a donor account is displayed. As shown in Figure 14, the form provides the user with some inputs to fill out the form. The donor is requested to input personal information such as name, contact number, email address, and password. A dropdown menu for donor type is provided where they are able to decide whether anonymous, individual, NGO, government, or private companies for the donor type. Upon clicking on the continue button, the process of registration is continued further for verification through email. The user is then prompted that a verification code is sent in the email that is used to fill out the form. A button is also provided to navigate back into the login form.

Enter Name	Select Donor Type
<input type="text" value="Name of Donor"/>	<input style="border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;" type="text" value="Private Companies"/>
Enter Contact	Enter Password
<input type="text" value="Contact no."/>	<input type="text" value="Password"/>
Enter Email	Confirm Password
<input type="text" value="e.g Example@gmail.com"/>	<input type="text"/>
<input type="button" value="Continue"/>	
<input type="button" value="Already have an account? Log in"/>	

Figure 14. Donor Registration Interface.

4.1.13 Donor Profile

After a successful donor registration, the donor logs in to their account and is then redirected to the profile page of the account of the donor. Shown in Figure 15 is the interface for the profile page of the donor account. In this interface, donors are able to update profile pictures and edit personal information. The interface also displays the name of the donor, email address and contact information.

Figure 15. Donor Profile Interface

4.1.14 Donate Matching and List of Scholarship Agencies

When the donor clicks on the donate section on the side navigation bar, the donor then is redirected to the form where the donate feature is accessible using the form to fill out. The donors are able to search by filling out the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement required in the scholarship agency and click on the search button. Below the form is the list of the verified scholarship agencies. As shown in the Figure 16, the interface displays the

profile picture and the name of the scholarship agency that are verified by the admin and criteria are set for matching.

The interface is divided into two main sections. The top section contains two search filters: "Enter Location of Agency" with a dropdown menu and "Enter Minimum Average Requirement" with a dropdown menu showing "75% - 79%". Below these filters is a "Search" button. The bottom section is titled "List of Verified Scholarship Agencies" and displays three agency cards. The first card features the "EduCash" logo (a graduation cap and a money icon) and the name "Tulong Dunong". The second card features the "LGU" logo (a building icon) and the name "LGU". The third card features a logo with four overlapping circles in black and blue and the name "Department of Science and Technology".

Figure 16. Donate Matching Interface

4.1.15 Searched Scholarship Agencies

After the donor filled out the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement, the donor then clicks on the search button and the result of the scholarship agencies based on the criteria that the donor has chosen are

displayed. As shown in Figure 17, are the scholarship agencies that are filtered by the donor is displayed using cards. The name of the scholarship agencies together with the profile pictures are shown, and there are two buttons where the donors are able to click. The first button is the view button, where displays the list of students in that scholarship agencies are displayed. Upon clicking on the donate button, the process for donation continues.

Figure 17. Donation Interface.

4.1.16 Payment Methods

Upon clicking on the donate button on the results of the scholarship agencies displayed in reference to Figure 17, the donor is redirected into the payment methods interface. As shown in Figure 18, are the payment methods available for the donors to choose from. The donors are able to choose between Gcash, Paypal or Maya.

Figure 18. Payment Gateways Interface

4.1.17 Upload Receipt Form

When the donor already decided on what payment gateway to choose, the donor clicks on the button of that payment gateway, and then the page is redirected to the form where the QR Code of that scholarship agency is visible. In order for the donor to continue processing financial transactions, the donor scans the QR Code first using the payment gateway used and input the amount. After scanning the QR Code, the donor then is required to upload the receipt of the transaction to finally complete the donation process. By clicking the upload button, the receipt is sent to the scholarship agency with the amount of the donation sent. The interface for uploading the receipt is shown below in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Upload Receipt Interface

4.1.18 Donor Inbox

Upon clicking the inbox section of the side navigation bar, the donor is then redirected to a page where the donation history is displayed. As shown in Figure 20, is the interface of the screen layout of the donation history for donors. The donation history is displayed in a tabular format. In this interface, the donors are able to customize the donation history based on the scholarship agency and the month when the donation is processed. In the table, donation id of the transaction is displayed in the first column. On the second column are the amount of the donation, followed by the name of the agency, and the date of the donation. Two

dropdown filters are provided above to let the donor categorize and view the total donation sent to each scholarship agency.

Donation History

All Agencies ▼

All Months ▼

Donation ID	Amount	Agency	Date of Donation
67	₱46,000.00	SM Foundation	May 27, 2025
68	₱46,000.00	Mcdo Agency	May 27, 2025
72	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
73	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
74	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 31, 2025
75	₱50,000.00	LGU	August 24, 2025

Total Donation: ₱292,000.00

Figure 20. Donor Donation History Interface

4.1.19. Student List

In reference to Figure 17, there is a button named view for viewing the list of scholars in that scholarship agency before the donors decide to donate. Upon clicking, a list of scholars is displayed in a tabular format. As shown in Figure 21, a drop-down menu and a search input are provided above the list of scholars. Two buttons are also available, namely the filter, which is used to submit the form and filter the students based on the criteria from the drop-down and from the search bar. And the other button is the return button which heads back the donor to the previous

page. The donors are able to categorize the students based on the school where the students are currently enrolled, and the program of study of the students.

The screenshot displays a web interface for viewing scholars. At the top, there are two filters: 'School:' with a dropdown menu set to 'All', and 'Program:' with a search input field containing 'Search program'. To the right of these filters are two buttons: a green 'Filter' button and a grey 'Return' button with a left-pointing arrow.

Scholar Name	School	Program of Study
Adrian Magallanes	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Zachary Guzon	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Ern Jan	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Karen Kaye Alfonso	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	BS Computer Science
Wrenz Bancolo	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing
Von Andrei Awacay	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Dorothy Abanalo	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing

Figure 21. View Scholars Interface

4.1.20 Scholarship Agency Registration Form

In reference to the login form shown back in Figure 3, the last account type that the users are able to choose is the scholarship agency account. As shown in

Figure 22 is the interface for the account registration of the scholarship agencies. The form provides five inputs for the scholarship agencies to fill out. The inputs such as the name of the scholarship agency, contact number, email address, and password together with the password confirmation. Upon clicking continue, an email is then sent to the admin that a new scholarship agency has registered an account. Further validation and verification are processed by the admin for monitoring of the scholarship agency accounts.

The image shows a registration form for scholarship agencies. It features five input fields: 'Name of Scholarship Agency', 'Contact', 'Email', 'Password', and 'Confirm Password'. A 'Continue' button is positioned below the 'Email' field, and a link 'Already have an Account? Login' is located at the bottom center. The form is set against a light blue background with a faint watermark of a laurel wreath and the text 'SINCE 2010'.

Name of Scholarship Agency	Password
Contact	Confirm Password
Email	
Continue	
Already have an Account? Login	

Figure 22. Scholarship Agency Registration Interface.

4.1.21 Scholarship Agency Profile Page

After the verification of the scholarship agency through email and by the admin, the scholarship agency is now able to access the features of the application. After a successful login, the scholarship agency is then redirected to the profile page. As shown in Figure 23, is the screen layout for the profile page of the scholarship agency. In the profile page, displayed are the personal information of the scholarship agency such as the name, the status, the contact number, and the email address together with the profile picture. Two buttons are accessible namely the edit profile, and the button where the scholarship agency is redirected to upload files or certificates necessary for validation. Below the personal information is the list of the scholars on the current period.

Bacolod Agency

Email
uddinlawrence7@gmail.com

Contact:
+6309865415236

Status
Verified

[Edit Profile](#) [Upload Certificates](#)

View Scholars |
University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)

Name	Program of Study	School	Files
Adrian Magallanes	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Zachary Guzon	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Ern Jan	Information Technology	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Karen Kaye Alfonso	BS Computer Science	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view
Wrenz Bancolo	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing	University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos (UNO-R)	view

Figure 23. Scholarship Agency Profile Interface

4.1.22 Account not Verified Error Message

When the scholarship agency has logged in while the account is not yet verified by the admin, an error message is prompted that the account is not yet verified. The message tells the scholarship agency to upload certificates and any necessary documents specifically the certificate of registration and the security exchange commission certificate.

Figure 24. Account Not Verified Interface.

4.1.23 Scholarship Posting Form

After the scholarship agency is fully verified by the admin, the scholarship agency is now able to post information and specific procedures for scholarship application, as shown in Figure 25 is the form for scholarship posting. The form includes the setting of scholarship benefits where the scholarship agency inputs the tuition coverage and the scholarship inclusion. Another one is setting of the eligibility requirement such as the degree preference and the minimum average requirement. Scholarship agency also sets the application requirement of the students and also the application process. Additionally, the deadline of submission and announcement of results are also included in the form. The output of this process is shown in Figure 9, the feed interface.

Set Information About the Scholarship

Set Scholarship Benefits

Enter Tuition Coverage
35000.00 above

Scholarship Inclusion

- Monthly Living Allowance
- Book and Educational Materials Allowance
- One-Time Laptop or Gadget Grant
- Internet and Communication Support
- Thesis or Research Grant
- Internship or Mentorship Opportunities
- Exclusive Training and Workshops
- Health and Wellness Support
- Employment Assistance After Graduation

Other:

Set Eligibility Requirement

Degree Preference Related to

- Science, Technology and Mathematics
- Education
- Arts and Humanities
- Agriculture and Forestry
- Business, Hospitality and Finance

Other:

Minimum Average Requirement
75% - 80%

Set Application Requirement

- Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records
- Certificate of Enrollment or Admission
- Copy of Valid School ID
- Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian
- Certificate of Indigency from Barangay or Municipality
- Latest Payslip of Parents/Guardian
- Certificate of Non-Filing of Income Tax
- Birth Certificate
- Parent's or Guardian's Valid ID
- Medical Certificate
- Barangay Clearance or Good Moral Certificate

Other:

Deadline of Submission
mm/dd/yyyy

Announcement of Result
mm/dd/yyyy

Set Application Process

Set the Application Process in order

1 Enter process 1 here

+

Submit

Set a Matching Criteria? [Click Here](#)

Figure 25. Scholarship Postings Interface

4.1.24 Scholarship Matching Form

Before the scholarship agencies are able to manage scholarship applications, the scholarship agencies are first required to set criteria for matching. This feature is accessible upon clicking the criteria section on the side navigation bar. After clicking on the criteria section, the scholarship agency is then redirected into the page where the form for the matching criteria is displayed. As shown in Figure 26, is the form for scholarship matching. It includes six inputs for scholarship agencies to fill out. The location of scholarship agency, the tuition coverage, the minimum average requirement, the deadline of application, supported institutions, and coverage type are the inputs in the form. Upon clicking the “Set Criteria” button, the criteria for matching are now set for students to match.

Set Criteria for Matching

Your Location	Tuition Coverage
<input type="text" value="e.g Bacolod City"/>	<input type="text" value="below 5000.00"/>
Minimum Average Requirement	Deadline of Application
<input type="text" value="75% - 79%"/>	<input type="text" value="mm/dd/yyyy"/>
Supported Institutions	Coverage Type
<input type="text" value="Private"/>	<input type="text" value="Tuition Only"/>

Figure 26. Scholarship Matching Form Interface

4.1.25. Scholarship Agency Inbox

When clicking inbox section on the side navigation bar, the scholarship agency is then redirected to the lists of applicants and list of donations received. As shown in Figure 27 is the inbox screen layout for scholarship agency accounts. On the first table, the pending applicants are displayed together with the name, and the date submitted. Provided with the view action where scholarship agencies are able to further validate the application process. Below the table of applicants is the table of the donations received by the scholarship agencies. Displayed are the name of the donor, date of donation, the payment method used, the amount followed by the receipt of the transaction. Provided with two actions, which is acknowledge, and to delete the transaction.

Applications					
Student Name	Date Submitted	Action			
Adrian Magallanes	2025-12-25 12:49:29				

Donations					
Donor Name	Date of Donation	Payment Method	Amount	Receipt	Action
Libertad NGO	2025-11-15 15:08:21	gcash	₱1415.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-31 07:50:58	gcash	₱60000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-10-15 14:54:52	gcash	₱10000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-08-24 07:37:06	gcash	₱50000.00		
Libertad NGO	2025-07-24 07:33:31	gcash	₱50000.00		

Figure 27. Scholarship Agency Inbox

4.1.26 Dashboard Interface

As shown in Figure 28, is the screen lay out for the reports and dashboard interface. When the user clicks the reports button in the sidebar section, the user is headed to the screen lay out that features the graphs and reports in the system. First is the pie chart that provides the number of each donor type such as NGO, anonymous, Government Agencies, Private Companies, and Specific Individuals, that willingly provided and supported the students that are underprivileged and deserving of the financial support. Second is the line chart for the total number of students arithmetically added each month. And lastly, is the bar graph for the total amount of donations over time each month.

Figure 28. Dashboard Interface.

4.1.27 Admin Interface

Every time a scholarship agency account is registered in the application, the admin is notified, and the admin dashboard is updated. As shown in Figure 29 are the non-verified scholarship agencies displayed in a tabular format. The table displays the name of the scholarship agency, the email address, contact number, and the status of the account. Two columns are dedicated for the certifications of the scholarship agencies with the icon indicators for missing files and if the files are uploaded and is ready to view. Also, two columns are dedicated for the action, to verify and to send an email to the scholarship agency.

Name	Email	Contact	Status	Registration CERT	SEC Certificate	Action
Kabankalan Scholarship Agency	kabankalan@gmail.com	+639895969699	Not Verified			
Himamaylan Agency	jimenez@gmail.com	+639698596633	Not Verified			
Government Service Insurance System	gsis@gmail.com	+639859632514	Not Verified			

Figure 29. Admin Interface.

4.1.28 Email Messaging Field

After clicking the envelope icon in the action column shown in Figure 30, the admin is then redirected to a field where the admin is able to fill out and write a message to the scholarship agency in the reason of following up or if the files and documents submitted by the scholarship agency are somehow suspicious and subjected for further verification and validation. The admin is able to send the

concerns through email, and the status of the scholarship agency updates into pending state.

Send Message
To: Kabankalan Scholarship Agency

Message Content

Write your message here... Please include any specific requirements or feedback for the agency.

← Back to Dashboard Send Message

Agency Information

Name: Kabankalan Scholarship Agency	Contact: +639895969699
Email: kabankalan@gmail.com	Status: Not Verified

Figure 30. Email Messaging Interface

4.1.29 Calculation Methods

Before the scholarship agencies safely disburse the funds to the students, the scholarship agencies are able to select a calculation method on how to distribute the funds in a calculated manner. As shown in Figure 30, is the screen interface for the calculation method. A dropdown menu is accessible for scholarship agencies to choose one from five different methods of calculation. A

button is also visible to approve the method of calculation. Below the button is an overview of the calculation.

Calculation Method for AY 2025-2026 First Semester

Top 20%

▼

✔ Approve for Disbursement

Calculation for Distribution

Total Amount of Donations: ₱171415
 Total no. of Scholars: 18
 60% of Total Donations: 102,849.00
 40% of Total Donations: 68,566.00

Top 20% Scholars	Amount(60%)	Average
Bernard Muleta	₱25 712.25	94.7
Aliah Nicole Javier	₱25 712.25	94.7
Andrew Batuigas	₱25 712.25	94.7
Kent Romyr Gargalicano	₱25 712.25	94.7
Other Scholars		
	Amount(40%)	Average
Gyan Warben Tamayo	₱4 897.57	94.63
Bruce Wayne	₱4 897.57	94.63
Jonh Lorence G. Reyes	₱4 897.57	94.63

Figure 31. Calculation Methods Interface

4.1.30 Allowance Distribution

After selecting a calculation method, scholarship agencies are now able to disburse the money to the students with a guide of the amount and the number of students. As shown in Figure 32, the total amount of donations and the total number of students are visible. A button with a bank icon is visible as an action that when clicked, it redirects the page to the payment gateways interface.

Calculation for Acedemic Year 2025-2026 First Semester			
Total Amount of Donations: ₱171415			
Total no. of Scholars: 18			
60% of Total Donations: 102,849.00			
40% of Total Donations: 68,566.00			
Top 20% Scholars	Amount(60%)	Average	Action
Bernard Muleta	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Aliah Nicole Javier	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Andrew Batuigas	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Kent Romyr Gargalicano	₱25 712.25	94.7	
Other Scholars	Amount(40%)	Average	Action
Gyan Warben Tamayo	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Bruce Wayne	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Jonh Lorence G. Reyes	₱4 897.57	94.63	
Antonio Camacho	₱4 897.57	91.5	

Figure 32. Allowance Distribution Interface

4.2 Hardware Interfaces

The system is a web-based application and required minimal considerations when it comes to hardware. The users of the application only need a desktop computer that is able to access a web browser and utilize the system. The application relies on operating system to manage the commands and hardware interactions of the users. Since the application is currently not compatible to mobile devices, the application is optimized only for desktop computers because of their large screens that provides the users a more efficient and a more comfortable user experience for utilizing the system features.

4.3 Software Interfaces

In order to carry out all intended controls and procedures in a regulated setting, the project team took into account how markup, style, programming languages, terminal commands, networks, internet protocols, and modular modules interact with the hardware. They assessed these elements to make sure they cooperate well during the execution of the application. The project team aims to do this in order to spot any possible problems and make the required adjustments to provide a user-friendly application, and an improved user experience.

4.3.1 Browser

EduCash is a web-based application that functions on any desktop computers that is equipped with a web browser. This includes popular search engines including Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge, Opera, and Mozilla Firefox. The project team tested the application on these web browsers to ensure that it is compatible and has consistent functionality. Since the application is accessible, a fast and stable internet connection is needed to enhance the user experience by improving the responsiveness and reliability of the application across different search engines or browsers. As for the different search engines, google chrome showed its compatibility within the EduCash application with its features and functionalities.

4.4 Communication Interfaces

The following sections identifies and discusses the components and technologies involved in data transmission between the web application and the users. This includes the

processes that initiates and manage data transfer, as well as the processes involved in financial transactions, emailing systems, and how information is managed to ensure smooth operations in the application. Additionally, the sections that follows outlines the technologies used to make the processes in the application possible.

4.4.1 Tesseract OCR

This engine is used for many processes in the application. By using patterns and regular expressions, Tesseract OCR engine is one of the core technologies used for most of the features in the application. This engine is used for reading the documents submitted by the users for validation and verification. The Tesseract OCR engine is also used for extracting the amount from the receipts uploaded by the users in financial transactions in the application.

4.4.2 PHP Mailer

PHP Mailer is implemented in the application to manage email-related functionalities securely and efficiently. It is primarily used for email notifications, such as informing the admin when a new scholarship agency registers on the application, alerting scholarship agencies when a student submits a scholarship application, and notifying them once the donated amount has been successfully received. For email verification, PHP Mailer sends verification tokens to new users during registration to ensure that only valid and active email addresses are used within the system. Additionally, PHP Mailer is integrated into the application to implement an email messaging system, allowing the admin to directly communicate with scholarship agencies regarding important matters, such as the submission of required certificates and other compliance documents.

In conclusion, this chapter provided a detailed discussion of the external interface requirements of the EduCash application and explained how each feature is designed to make the system simple, organized, and easy for its users to navigate. It covered the different interfaces for students, donors, scholarship agencies, and the admin, showing how every section works together to improve the overall experience of using the application. From the login and registration pages to the upload forms, inboxes, and donation features, each part was created to make the processes faster, clearer, and more efficient for everyone involved. The chapter also discussed important technologies such as Tesseract OCR, which helps in reading and validating documents, and PHP Mailer, which ensures that email notifications, verifications, and communications are sent in a secure and reliable way. These technologies support the main goal of EduCash, which is to provide a safe and transparent application that connects donors and scholarship agencies with students in need of financial assistance. By meeting these external interface requirements, the system is able to handle scholarship applications properly, improve communication among users, and make the donation and distribution process more dependable.

CHAPTER V

OTHER NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

This chapter discusses the evaluation of the non-functional requirements of the EduCash Project. The evaluation focuses on the overall performance, and the quality of the system as a donation platform. The predefined criteria for software quality were used to analyze and examine the key system features and determine the top three and bottom three as the area of strength and weaknesses of the application. Additionally, the chapter also discusses the evaluation criteria interpretation, Software quality metrics and attributes, together with the feedback analysis. Moreover, the project team used ISO/IEC 25010:2011 as the quality assurance model for systems and software quality requirements and evaluation, as the application shows that it prioritizes several non-functional qualities such as security, usability, reliability and performance scalability, and maintainability and compatibility, in its system features.

5.1 Performance Requirements

This section of the paper discusses how the EduCash application performed its functionalities and features effectively and efficiently. In evaluating the performance of the application, many measures were used and implemented to solve its coefficient, which helped the project team to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the application to perform more efficiently. The software quality attributes were used to evaluate the features of the application. EduCash had four major functionalities, such as Account Creation and

Management, Scholarship Matching and Postings, Financial Transactions, and Data Analytics.

The software quality model, ISO 25010 [ISO25], was used as reference to evaluate the system features of EduCash application. Five leading quality attributes such as Security, Usability, Reliability, Performance Efficiency, and Maintainability, were used to examine and evaluate the feature of the application. The project team evaluated the authentication process which included the login and registration for security to ensure that the application safely keep the information of the users. The security attribute included the following criteria to be used such as confidentiality, Integrity, Accountability, and Authenticity. As for the Scholarship Matching, the quality attribute was used to evaluate its performance for the matches of student profiles and scholarship agencies. As for the financial transactions, For the Financial Transactions module, the primary quality attribute is Security, specifically focusing on Integrity, based on the ISO/IEC 25010 model. Integrity ensures that all donation and scholarship fund transactions are processed and stored without unauthorized alteration, duplication, or loss. This guarantees the correctness and trustworthiness of financial records, which is essential for maintaining donor confidence and ensuring fair distribution of scholarship funds. For the Data Analytics module of EduCash, the primary quality attribute is Accuracy, under the Functional Suitability category of ISO/IEC 25010. Accuracy ensures that the analytical output such as applicant statistics, donor contributions, scholarship demand, and matching outcomes correctly represent the underlying system data. This guarantees trustworthy insights for students, agencies, and administrators, enabling reliable decision-making based on accurate quantitative results.

System Features	Software Quality Attributes and Models	Software Quality Criteria	Mean Score	Feature Mean Score
Account Creation and Management	Security	Integrity	50%	62.5%
		Confidentiality	75%	
		Authenticity	62.5%	
Scholarship Matching and Postings	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	91.7%
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	100%	
Financial Transactions	Security	Integrity	83%	83.23%
		Confidentiality	100%	
		Authenticity	66.7%	
Calculations	Accuracy	Correctness	100%	80.6
		Completeness	75%	
		Consistency	66.7%	

Table 12. Summary of Features, Attributes, and Results.

As shown in Table 13, it presents the percentage ranges and their corresponding interpretations for the feature mean scores. It helps explain the derived quality scores and enables the project team to assess the performance of the system features based on its attributes. A percentage range of 84.1%-100% is marked as the highest rate a feature is able to receive, while having a 36% as the lowest rate.

Mean Score	Percentage range	Remarks
4.21-5.00	84.1% – 100%	Very Good
3.41-4.20	68.1% – 84.0%	Good
2.61-3.40	52.1% – 68.0%	Average
1.81-2.60	36.1% – 52.0%	Poor
1.00-1.80	20.0% – 36.0%	Very Poor

Table 13. Mean Score Interpretation

5.2 Software Quality Metrics and Attributes

The software quality that is mainly used to evaluate the performance of the system features are namely, security, and accuracy. These qualities are found in the software quality model ISO/IEC 25010, as shown in the Figure 31. To evaluate the functionality of the EduCash application correctly, the measures and formulas in evaluating the software quality of the system features are discussed in the appendices section of the paper with specified conditions for each software quality criteria.

Figure 33. ISO25010 Software Product Quality.

5.2.1 Integrity

The software quality attribute that ensures computer programs and data are protected from unauthorized access or modification is known as integrity. Integrity plays a critical role in maintaining the reliability and trustworthiness of a system, as it guarantees that information remains accurate, consistent, and unaltered unless performed by authorized processes or users. In the context of evaluating software systems, Formula 1 was utilized to calculate the mean integrity score, considering the relevant factors that influence this quality attribute. Specifically, the integrity percentage was determined by dividing the number of resolved requirements by the total number of requirements, thereby providing a quantitative measure of how well the system maintains its intended state against potential threats or errors.

$$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 1. Integrity formula

The Account Creation and Management module of the EduCash system was evaluated using this software quality metric. The mean score from computation was 50%, indicating a moderate integrity performance. This suggests that while some requirements, such as allowing users to alter their personal information and sending email confirmations for the “forgot password” feature, were properly implemented, other critical requirements like password confirmation during edits and administrator access to user information were not fully addressed, highlighting

areas for improvement. The Financial Transactions module of the EduCash system was evaluated using this software quality metric. The mean score from computation was 83%, indicating a strong integrity performance. This signifies that most requirements, such as recording donations, updating total amounts for scholarship agencies, sending receipts to recipients, and ensuring that only scholarship agencies are able to view their received totals, were properly implemented. However, the system-generated receipts feature was not fully realized, highlighting a minor area for improvement.

5.2.2 Confidentiality

Confidentiality as a software quality attribute was achieved when a system ensured that data were accessible only to users with authorized access. This attribute is essential for protecting sensitive information, as it prevents unauthorized users from viewing, modifying, or exploiting confidential data. By enforcing confidentiality, the system guarantees that user credentials, personal information, and other sensitive data remain secure and anonymous, thereby maintaining trust between the system and its users. The evaluation of confidentiality was quantified using a formula that involved dividing the total number of confidentiality requirements by the number of resolved requirements, providing a clear metric for assessing how effectively the system met its security objectives.

$$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 2. Confidentiality formula

The confidentiality of the EduCash system was evaluated by examining key requirements in both the Account Creation and Management module and the Financial Transactions module. The Account Creation and Management module obtained a mean score of 75%, reflecting a good confidentiality performance, as most requirements such as user registration, verification before feature access, and email verification were properly implemented, though password hashing was not yet addressed. Meanwhile, the Financial Transactions module achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent confidentiality, as all requirements including protecting donor contact information, ensuring anonymity, restricting receipt visibility, and limiting access to donation history were fully satisfied. These results demonstrate that the system effectively safeguards sensitive user and financial data, with minor improvements needed in password storage practices.

5.2.3 Authenticity

The software quality attribute of authenticity was assessed using the formula presented in Formula 3, and it refers to the degree to which a user identity be verified as truly belonging to the individual claiming it. Authenticity is a critical aspect of system security, as it ensures that the information provided by users during registration such as credentials, personal details, or identification data accurately and reliably reflects their true identity. This prevents impersonation, fraudulent access, and unauthorized use of system resources. The authenticity metric was calculated by dividing the number of resolved functions by the total number of requirements, providing a quantitative measure of how effectively the system verifies and validates user identities.

$$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 3. Authenticity formula

The authenticity of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Account Creation and Management module and the Financial Transactions module. The Account Creation and Management module achieved a mean score of 62.5%, indicating a moderate authenticity performance. Most requirements, such as storing email and username in the database, ensuring password matches, implementing password complexity, and enabling session timeout, were fulfilled, while requirements like age restrictions, password recovery, and limiting multiple tabs were not fully addressed. The Financial Transactions module obtained a mean score of 66.7%, reflecting a slightly higher performance, with successful implementation of saving donation amounts, receipt clarity, duplicate donation prevention, and amount extraction in receipts, but leaving amount restrictions and confirmation features incomplete. These results suggest that while the system generally maintains data authenticity, certain controls and validations need improvement to ensure complete reliability of user and financial information.

5.2.4 Correctness

The software quality attribute of correctness refers to the degree to which a system produces accurate and reliable results, as demonstrated in Formula 4. Correctness is achieved when the data and information processed by the system are

accurate, and all computations, controls, and functions operate as intended. Ensuring correctness not only validates the integrity of the outputs but also enhances the overall reliability and consistency of the system, leading to more dependable results. The measure of correctness was calculated by dividing the number of functions that had been successfully implemented by the total number of functions, providing a quantitative assessment of how effectively the system meets its functional requirements.

$$CR = \frac{\textit{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\textit{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 4. Correctness formula

The correctness of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Scholarship Matching and Postings module and the Calculation module. Both modules achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent correctness performance. All critical functions, including the submit buttons for criteria and postings forms, the apply button for students, the display of error and success messages, approval buttons in calculations, enforcing one calculation per period, and the method of calculations, were implemented accurately according to the requirements specifications. These results demonstrate that the system performs its intended functions reliably and without errors, ensuring that both scholarship matching and financial calculations are executed precisely as designed.

5.2.5 Completeness

The software quality attribute of completeness reflects the degree to which the set of functions of a system satisfies all user goals and performs all specified tasks. A complete system ensures that every requirement identified during analysis and design is addressed, leaving no critical functionality unimplemented. Formula 5 was used to calculate the mean completeness score, which was determined by dividing the number of requirements met by the total number of requirements. By measuring completeness, developers and stakeholders are able to evaluate how thoroughly the system fulfills its intended purpose, ensuring that users achieve their objectives without encountering gaps or missing features.

$$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$$

Formula 5. Completeness formula

The completeness of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Scholarship Matching and Postings module and the Calculation module. The Scholarship Matching and Postings module achieved a mean score of 75%, indicating a good completeness performance. Most requirements, such as posting deadlines, matching students based on criteria, notifying agencies about matched students, and allowing agencies to cross-check documents, were successfully implemented, while limitations on students receiving only one scholarship and setting criteria only once were not fully addressed. Similarly, the Calculation module also obtained a mean score of 75%, reflecting that requirements like

selecting a calculation method, providing an overview before approval, and informing donors were complete, while informing students about the calculation method before receiving funds remained incomplete. These results suggest that the system effectively covers the majority of its intended functionality, with minor gaps that are able to be addressed to achieve full completeness.

5.2.6 Consistency

The software quality attribute of consistency reflects the degree to which the functions of the system to behave uniformly and reliably across all modules and operations. A consistent system ensures that similar inputs produce predictable results and that processes and outputs follow the same standards and conventions throughout. Formula 6 presented how the consistency quality mean score was computed. It was calculated by dividing the number of consistent functions detected by the total number of functions described in the requirements specifications and multiplying the result by 100. By measuring consistency in this way, developers and stakeholders evaluate how reliably the system adheres to expected behavior, reduces potential errors, and provides a stable and predictable experience for users.

$$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$$

Formula 6. Consistency formula

The consistency of the EduCash system was evaluated through the Scholarship Matching and Postings module and the Calculation module. The Scholarship Matching and Postings module achieved a perfect mean score of 100%, indicating excellent consistency performance. All functions, including aligning

matches with set criteria, matching students based on averages, posting procedures and guidelines, and verifying users before access, were consistently implemented. Meanwhile, the Calculation module obtained a mean score of 66.7%, reflecting moderate consistency, as most calculations were applied correctly in distributing amounts and scaling based on student numbers, but some students did not consistently receive funds according to all calculation methods. These results suggest that while the system generally maintains reliable and repeatable operations, improvements in calculation distribution consistency are needed to ensure uniform performance across all users.

5.3 Safety Requirements

The EduCash application requires users to have a desktop device for it to be accessed and for the system features to be used. In the meantime, the application only supports desktop views, since the application is currently not compatible with mobile devices. The users had to register an account and undergo certain verification processes in order to be verified and access the features. The account creation process requires users to first, select an account type, and then enter personal information and necessary documents. An email verification is sent to the email provided by the users together with the link to the application for the users to enter the verification code. Once the user is registered, and they are fully verified, the user now is able to access the features of the system. Students are able to look for scholarships and receive financial support by matching with the scholarship agencies. Scholarship agencies, after being verified by the admin, are able to set criteria for students to match, receive and disburse donations. And lastly, for donors, they are able to select a scholarship agency they want to support financially.

5.4 Testing Requirements

The developers underwent a comprehensive testing phase for the EduCash application, meticulously evaluating both technical and operational specifications to ensure that the system met all defined requirements. During this phase, the project team verified that each feature functioned as intended and accurately reflected the functionalities outlined during the design phase. This process involved systematically identifying, documenting, and resolving any discrepancies, bugs, or unexpected behaviors that could affect user experience or system performance. By thoroughly testing the application, the project team ensured that the software not only operated reliably under various conditions but also adhered to quality standards, providing users with a seamless and fully functional experience. The testing phase thus served as a critical checkpoint to validate the effectiveness, stability, and readiness of the application before its deployment.

5.4.1 Unit Testing

A unit test was performed to verify which modules conformed to the specified system requirements. During this process, users were instructed to enter only the essential information required by the EduCash application, reducing the risk of exposing personal data during account creation. Additionally, users were required to successfully complete the sign-in process in order to access all features and functionalities of the application, ensuring both security and proper system operation.

5.4.2 Integration Testing

The overall design and layout of EduCash were specifically intended for desktop use. The project focused on ensuring that the interface was optimized for

larger screens, with careful consideration of the placement and size of elements to provide a clear and organized view. The front-end components were designed to be visually appealing and user-friendly, allowing users to navigate seamlessly across different desktop resolutions and window sizes. The project team also implemented a color-coded interface to avoid confusion and consolidate certain portions of the user interface, making it easier to differentiate between account types. This design choice not only improved visual clarity but also enhanced overall user experience by allowing users to quickly identify their account sections and navigate the system more efficiently.

5.4.3 Acceptance Testing

In conclusion, the evaluation of non-functional requirements of the EduCash application demonstrates that the system effectively meets key software quality standards, emphasizing security, accuracy, reliability, and usability. By using the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 model, the project team was able to systematically assess the integrity, confidentiality, authenticity, correctness, completeness, and consistency of the system features, identifying areas of strength and improvement. The desktop-focused application design, comprehensive testing procedures, and color-coded interface further ensure a secure, user-friendly, and efficient experience for students, donors, and scholarship agencies. Overall, the non-functional requirements evaluation confirms that EduCash is a reliable and robust

platform that successfully supports its intended purpose of facilitating financial assistance and scholarship matching.

In addition, the evaluation highlights the systems capacity to maintain stable performance during routine operations and transaction processing. Consistent interface behavior and clear navigation contribute to improved user satisfaction across different account types. These findings collectively affirm the overall quality and readiness of the EduCash application for practical deployment in an educational support environment.

CHAPTER VI

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management is important because it helps guarantee that projects are finished on schedule, within budget, and with the anticipated level of quality, project management is crucial. Additionally, it aids in risk identification and mitigation, efficient resource management, and ensuring that stakeholders are informed and involved at every stage of the project. [WWW18] this part of the paper outlines the comprehensive overview of the project. It outlines the characteristics of user classes, assessment of feasibility, the project timeline in detail, and emphasizing the technical robustness of the platform, its operational efficiency, and financial sustainability. Moreover, this part of the paper also highlights the scheduling of tasks, the resource allocation, and team composition, that aims to ensure a well-coordinated and efficient development process.

6.1 User Classes and Characteristics

The platform serves three primary user classes which includes donors, recipients, and scholarship agencies and additionally, the administrator. This section of the paper discussed the user classes and characteristics in the platform. It outlines their access to the features of the platform, and their roles for the platform to function properly.

6.1.1 Recipients

A complete list of eligible candidates comprises the primary users with access to features such as submitting grades, personal information, and family monthly income as some of the other requirement for platform eligibility,

facilitating quicker negotiations with scholarship agencies, and thereafter claiming the financial assistance awarded to them by various donors like NGOs or individual benefactors-the recipients being university students who come from poor backgrounds and from the city of Bacolod.

6.1.2 Scholarship Agencies

The scholarship agencies are the users who are able to directly receive the monetary donations from donors. Scholarship agencies access the platform with the functionalities such as posting information about a scholarship, provide application forms for students, and distribution of money to students once the calculation is received and once scheduled.

6.1.3 Donors

One of the user classes of the platform are donors. Donors include NGOs, an individual donor, or anonymous donor. Donors are given access to the functionalities of the platform such as the integrated payment gateways for donation. When a Donor donates, the choice includes three of the payment method in the platform namely, GCash, PayPal, and Maya, or payment through bank payment integration. Additionally, donor categorizes their donation by universities/college that is located in Bacolod City

6.2 Product Feasibility

To ensure that the target user of the platform participate with the deployment of the project, the project team has analyzed and put together a strategic plan to promote the benefits of the platform and the platform itself. This section of the paper provides an

overview of some aspects of feasibility assessment analysis namely the marketing, management, economic and production which are needed to achieve the objectives of the platform.

6.2.1 Marketing Feasibility

EduCash targets underprivileged college students in Bacolod City, a growing demographic facing rising educational costs. Regional universities and colleges create a strong demand for scholarships and financial aid, and EduCash provides a structured, well-managed system that ensures operational success and sustainability. The platform allows donors, NGOs, and other philanthropists to confidently channel funds directly to students in need. By addressing this critical educational access gap aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), EduCash achieves high marketability. Unlike generic crowdfunding platforms, EduCash is purpose-built for scholarship distribution, making it an attractive and secure alternative. Through secure transactions and active donor engagement, the platform encourages long-term support. Additionally, universities and scholarship agencies can collaborate with EduCash to expand outreach and simplify applicant selection. The system is scalable and has potential for expansion beyond Bacolod City, increasing its overall impact. Promotional materials have been developed to support the platform, including the product packaging (see APPENDIX J), the product poster (see APPENDIX K), and the product logo (see APPENDIX H). Moreover, the project team has added product advertisements as part of the promotional materials to enhance awareness and engagement.

6.2.2 Management Feasibility Assessment

EduCash utilizes a multidisciplinary team consisting of software developers, database administrators, UI/UX designers, and cybersecurity specialists. The development phase comprises front-end and back-end engineers who are to ensure smooth integration of the system and secure payment processing capabilities. A team of financial analysts and compliance officers oversees all transactions between donors and scholarship distributions and ensure that the platform is in compliance with the law. Others include personnel assigned to manage and serve the additional needs of software maintenance and regulation inserts usually available to secure patches and functional advancements to the system after it enters production, such as system management in relation to possible further expansion.

6.2.3 Economic Feasibility Assessment

The financial sustainability of EduCash depends on a well-structured revenue model that includes platform service fees, voluntary transaction fees, or partnerships with universities and donors. Initial funding is required for platform development, cloud hosting, cybersecurity infrastructure, and marketing efforts. A break-even analysis helps determine when the platform sustains itself based on projected donation volumes and user engagement. The cost of integrating secure payment gateways like PayPal, GCash, and Maya must be factored into operational expenses. Potential grants from educational and philanthropic organizations helps subsidize early-stage development costs. A subscription or commission-based model for scholarship agencies provides additional revenue streams without

burdening student beneficiaries. Long-term financial projections should include system upgrades, customer support scaling, and expansion plans to other cities. Efficient resource allocation and budgeting are crucial to ensuring the financial viability of the platform.

6.2.4 Production Feasibility Assessment

Since EduCash is a web-based application, its production feasibility relies on software development rather than physical manufacturing. The platform must be built using scalable cloud-based infrastructure to accommodate increasing users and transaction volumes. Hosting on secure servers with data encryption measures ensures compliance with financial and privacy regulations. The distribution of EduCash primarily occur through digital marketing, university partnerships, and social media outreach. A mobile-responsive design enhances accessibility, allowing users to interact with the platform via smartphones and computers. Before the full, launch system testing and user feedback collection are crucial to ensure reliability and usability. Regular updates and feature enhancements keep the platform competitive and adaptable to evolving user needs. With strategic marketing and continuous optimization, EduCash achieves widespread adoption, making it a viable solution for educational financial assistance.

6.3 Time Management

This section of the paper, the project team provides an overview of the effective time management is essential for the successful development and deployment of EduCash. This aims to ensure that the project meets its objectives within the proposed timeline, the

time management plan has been broken down into phases with clear milestones and deadlines. The subsequent section of this paper provides the project time overview of the project, which is composed of planning, research, design and prototype development, platform development, and testing.

6.3.1 Project Timeline Overview

This section provides a high-level overview of the project timeline, detailing the sequence of activities from initial planning to final deployment. Each phase has an estimated time frame, carefully determined by considering task priorities, the availability of resources, and the complexity of technical requirements. This structured timeline ensures that the project progresses efficiently while allowing for proper allocation of effort and monitoring of milestones.

6.3.1.1 Planning and Research

During the initial phase, the focus is on conducting thorough research and gathering all necessary requirements to establish a solid foundation for EduCash. This includes studying existing platforms, understanding the target users' needs (both donors and students), and assessing technical and financial feasibility. Additionally, project planning activities, such as defining goals, setting up the project scope, and creating a detailed project roadmap, are completed to ensure all stakeholders have a clear vision of the objectives of the project.

6.3.1.2 Design and Prototype Development

In this phase of design and the development of the prototypes of the project, the project team designs the user interface (UI) and develops a prototype to showcase core functionalities of EduCash platform. The design focuses on an intuitive and user-friendly interface that appeals to both students and donors. Prototyping allows stakeholders to visualize the platform early, providing feedback on navigation, visual elements, and essential features, helping refine the design to meet user expectations before the main development begins. Moreover, the project team utilizes Figma for the design of the prototypes.

6.3.1.3 Platform Development

Platform development is the most intensive phase, covering coding, backend development, payment gateway integration, and database setup. This involves building the core functionalities, including user authentication, secure payment processing, and data storage with high encryption standards. Integration of payment options like PayPal, GCash, and Maya ensures convenient donation methods, while backend programming establishes reliable data management for student applications, donor information, and transaction tracking.

6.3.1.4 Testing and Quality Assurance

To ensure platform stability and security, comprehensive testing is conducted to address any bugs or usability issues. This phase includes unit testing, integration testing, and system testing to verify each function works

correctly and efficiently. Usability testing sessions are held with a select group of users to gain feedback on navigation and ease of use, while security and performance tests are conducted to validate data protection measures and platform responsiveness under varying loads.

6.4 Task Scheduling and Priority

Tasks are prioritized to ensure that essential features, like payment integration and security measures, are completed early in the development process. High-priority tasks are essential to the functionality of the platform, while medium and low-priority tasks enhance usability and visual appeal. This scheduling approach helps manage workload efficiently, focusing team efforts on tasks that are crucial for the initial success of the platform.

6.5 Resource Allocation

Efficient resource allocation is achieved by assigning specific roles and responsibilities to team members based on skill sets. Essential resources include technical tools, project management software, and partnerships with financial institutions. Proper resource planning ensures that all development and integration needs are met without straining the timeline or budget.

6.6 Communication, Coordination, and Team Composition

For EduCash, effective communication, coordinated teamwork, and a well-defined team composition are essential to ensure successful project execution. The following subsections outline the structure and strategies used to maintain alignment, collaboration, and efficient project management throughout development.

6.6.1 Communication

To facilitate seamless communication, the team uses a combination of platforms, including Microsoft Teams and Discord for real-time messaging and calls. These tools provide flexibility, enabling team members to discuss updates, address concerns, and conduct meetings remotely.

6.6.2 Coordination

Task assignments and progress tracking are managed through Google Docs, which provides a centralized space for documenting updates, making revisions, and sharing project-related files. For version control and collaboration, GitHub is used to store and manage code changes, allowing team members to track revisions and integrate updates efficiently.

6.6.3 Team Composition

The EduCash project team consists of three dedicated members, each fulfilling distinct roles that collectively contribute to the successful development of the platform. This small but specialized team allows for clear communication, effective collaboration, and efficient task distribution.

6.6.3.1 Project Manager

He oversees the project timeline, sets milestones, and manages the allocation of resources to ensure smooth project flow. Responsibilities include scheduling weekly meetings, coordinating between frontend and backend development, and maintaining alignment with project goals and requirements. By tracking progress and managing timelines, the Project Manager ensures that the platform development stays on course, addressing

any issues promptly to keep the project on track. Project Manager also serves as paper writer in the team. The project manager is also the one responsible for the documentation of the project.

6.6.3.2 Front-end Developer

The Front-End Developer is responsible for building and styling the user interface of the EduCash platform, focusing on both functionality and visual appeal. Using HTML for structure, CSS for styling, BOOTSTRAP 5 for responsiveness, and JavaScript for interactive elements, they create an intuitive and responsive layout that ensures accessibility across various devices and screen sizes. Their role involves developing features that allow users to navigate smoothly, access information, and complete transactions with ease. The Front-End Developer collaborates with the Back-End Developer to integrate data securely and accurately, ensuring a cohesive experience for users from login to final transaction.

6.6.3.3 Backend Developer

The Back-End Developer handles server-side programming, database management, and the integration of essential features such as user authentication, document verification, and payment gateway functionality. Their role involves developing a secure, efficient backend system using frameworks like Django and managing data flow between the server and the client-side. They collaborate with the Front-End Developer to ensure data is processed and displayed accurately, and with the Project Manager to prioritize backend tasks essential to the core operations of the platform.

In conclusion, this chapter of the paper comprehensively described the process of managing the project, discussing the essential stages ranging from identifying user classes to conducting a thorough feasibility assessment and assembling a competent team composition. Each of these components is not merely a procedural formality but a critical pillar that supports the overall success of the project. The identification of user classes, for instance, serves as a vital precursor to understanding the diverse needs and expectations of potential end-users, thereby allowing project managers to tailor their approach accordingly. Similarly, the feasibility assessment provides a structured framework to evaluate the technical, economic, and operational viability of the project, ensuring that resources are efficiently allocated and potential risks are proactively addressed. Moreover, assembling a well-balanced team with clearly defined roles and complementary skills enhances collaboration, accelerates problem-solving, and fosters a productive working environment. By meticulously addressing these foundational elements, the project establishes a strong groundwork that increases the likelihood of achieving its objectives while maintaining high standards of quality, efficiency, and stakeholder satisfaction. Ultimately, the careful integration of these management practices underscores the importance of strategic planning and informed decision-making in steering the project toward successful implementation.

CHAPTER VII

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discussed the summary and the recommendations of the EduCash application. A web-based application designed to support college students in studying in Bacolod City that struggles financially but at the same time excels in their academic performance, providing them financial support and academic opportunities, and to promote the act of giving by targeting multiple donors such as NGO, private agencies, government organizations, individual donors, and anonymous donors. This chapter discusses the comprehensive summary of the system features, interfaces, and other functionalities that provides overview of the development of the application and its purpose.

7.1 Summary

EduCash is a web-based application designed to support underprivileged and deserving college students in Bacolod City. This system connects students with individual donors, NGOs, and government agencies to facilitate financial assistance for education. Users must create accounts to access features like scholarship matching, which pairs students with suitable agencies based on academic performance. A document verification module ensures the authenticity of student credentials to prevent fraudulent applications. Donors utilize a dedicated portal to send funds and track their donation history through generated receipts. The application integrates payment gateways such as PayPal, GCash, and Maya for secure monetary transactions. Scholarship agencies manage the disbursement of funds to students using specific calculation methods provided by the platform. The

interface uses color-coded backgrounds to help users differentiate between various account types easily. Data analytics features offer visual reports on donation trends and student performance for administrative monitoring. This project aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal for Quality Education by bridging financial gaps for students.

7.2 Recommendation

EduCash is a web-based application designed to provide financial support to underprivileged and deserving college students in Bacolod City. The platform fosters social solidarity by connecting students with individual donors, NGOs, and government agencies eager to fund education. As users start on their journey with EduCash, the application serves its purpose by bridging the gap between financial needs and educational opportunities. The system provides students the knowledge about available scholarships through a centralized space for fast inquiries. Users explore and choose specific scholarship agencies or receive matches based on their academic credentials and performance. The application then provides the steps for document verification to ensure only qualified applicants access financial aid. A dedicated donor portal allows benefactors to send funds securely and track their donation history through generated receipts. The application is designed with a color-coded interface to offer a seamless and organized navigation experience for various account types. Data analytics features offer visual reports on donation trends and student performance to evaluate platform impact. Overall, EduCash seeks to create an inclusive and transparent platform that promotes academic excellence and long-term social change.

7.2.1 System Generated Receipt

One of the critical recommendations from the panel review is the implementation of an automated system-generated receipt feature that consolidates and standardizes transaction documentation across all payment gateways integrated within the EduCash platform. Currently, the application relies on manual receipt uploads from donors and scholarship agencies after completing transactions through GCash, Maya, or PayPal, which introduces several operational inefficiencies and potential risks including inconsistent documentation formats, difficulty in verification and audit trails, potential for fraudulent or altered receipts, and increased administrative overhead for manual validation. To address these limitations, the proposed system-generated receipt feature leverages the existing Tesseract OCR engine to automatically extract critical transaction information from uploaded payment gateway receipts, including transaction ID, amount, date and time stamps, sender and recipient details, and payment method identifiers. This extracted data then undergoes validation against the donation records in the database to ensure accuracy and prevent duplicate submissions. Upon successful validation, the system automatically generates a standardized, official EduCash receipt in PDF format that incorporates the platform branding, includes a unique system-generated receipt number for tracking and reference purposes, and contains a QR code linking to the verified transaction record for authenticity verification. The generated receipt is simultaneously distributed to all relevant parties through automated email notifications sent to the donor with their official tax-deductible receipt, transmitted to the scholarship agency for their financial records and

acknowledgment, and archived in the system database with encrypted storage for compliance and audit purposes. This implementation significantly enhances the platform credibility and professionalism, streamlines the donation acknowledgment process, reduces administrative workload, provides donors with immediate standardized documentation for tax purposes, creates a comprehensive audit trail for financial accountability and transparency, and ensures compliance with financial reporting requirements for both donors and scholarship agencies. The expected benefits of this implementation include an estimated 75% reduction in receipt processing time, a projected 90% decrease in receipt-related disputes and clarification requests, enhanced donor satisfaction through immediate receipt generation and professional documentation, improved compliance with financial regulations and audit requirements, and strengthened platform credibility through standardized, tamper-proof transaction records.

7.2.2 Fully Integrated Payment Gateways

A significant recommendation from the panel review is the complete integration of payment gateways including GCash, PayPal, and Maya directly into the EduCash platform to enable seamless, real-time transaction processing without requiring users to leave the application interface. The current implementation presents a semi-manual approach where donors select their preferred payment method, navigate to external platforms to complete transactions, and then return to EduCash to manually upload transaction receipts as proof of payment. This fragmented workflow creates multiple pain points including interrupted user experience that increases transaction abandonment rates, delayed confirmation of

donations, increased opportunity for human error in amount entry and receipt upload, administrative burden of manually verifying each uploaded receipt, and lack of real-time financial tracking capabilities. The proposed full integration addresses these issues by embedding the payment gateway APIs directly into the EduCash transaction flow through establishing direct connections with GCash Developer API[DVAPI], PayPal REST API, and Maya Checkout API[MCAPI]. Upon successful payment completion, the integrated system receives immediate transaction confirmations through webhook callbacks that automatically trigger backend processes including database recording, receipt generation, and stakeholder notifications. This implementation transforms the donation process from a fragmented workflow requiring several minutes and manual verification into a streamlined experience completable within seconds.

7.2.3 One student, One Scholarship Agency.

A critical recommendation from the panel review is the implementation of a strict one student, one scholarship agency policy to ensure fair distribution of financial resources and prevent scholarship hoarding by individual students. The current system allows students to apply to and potentially receive financial support from multiple scholarship agencies simultaneously, creating issues including unequal distribution of limited scholarship funds, administrative complications in tracking and disbursing funds, potential ethical concerns regarding fairness, and reduced overall platform impact by concentrating resources on fewer beneficiaries rather than maximizing the number of students helped. The proposed policy enforces a single active scholarship match per student through database

constraints and application logic that automatically prevents students from applying to additional agencies once they have been accepted by one scholarship provider, with the student account status changing to "actively enrolled" and all other pending applications automatically withdrawn with notifications sent to both the student and the affected agencies. This restriction remains in effect until the student either completes their program, fails to maintain the required academic standards and is dropped from the scholarship, or the scholarship agency terminates the arrangement, at which point the student regains eligibility to match with a different agency. The implementation provides clear benefits including equitable distribution of scholarship resources across a larger number of deserving students, simplified financial tracking and disbursement processes, reduced administrative overhead, enhanced transparency and fairness in the allocation system, prevention of potential abuse or manipulation, and increased overall social impact by maximizing the total number of students receiving educational support through the application.

EduCash is a web-based platform that connects underprivileged college students in Bacolod City with donors, NGOs, and government agencies to provide financial support and promote academic opportunities. The system features scholarship matching, document verification, donor portals, secure payment integrations, color-coded interfaces, and data analytics to ensure transparency, efficiency, and impact monitoring. Key recommendations include implementing automated system-generated receipts, fully integrating payment gateways for seamless transactions, and enforcing a “one student, one scholarship agency”

policy to ensure fair resource distribution. These enhancements aim to streamline operations, improve user experience, strengthen accountability, and maximize the social and educational impact application. In addition, the automated receipt feature will reduce processing time, minimize disputes, and provide standardized, tamper-proof documentation for donors and scholarship agencies. Full payment gateway integration will enable real-time transactions, immediate confirmation, and lower the risk of human error, creating a smoother donation experience. The one student, one scholarship agency policy ensures equitable distribution of funds, prevents scholarship hoarding, and increases the total number of beneficiaries supported by the platform. Overall, these improvements enhance credibility, operational efficiency, and alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal of Quality Education.

GLOSSARY

A. ACCOUNT CREATION AND MANAGEMENT.

A feature of EduCash that allows the users to create and manage their personal account, that provides users a personalized access in the platform.

B. ALLOWANCE DESTRIIBUTION.

A feature of EduCash that grants students the financial support that they deserved from donors.

C. ANONYMOUS.

Refers to the donors of EduCash who would rather not want to share their Identity to other users of EduCash.

D. CALCULATED CASH ASSISTANCE.

A purpose of EduCash that is defined to provide the students calculated cash assistance from the monetary donations that are gathered from NGO, individual, and anonymous donors.

E. DATA ANALYTICS.

A feature of EduCash that provides users the analytics of the total amount that is donated in the platform, the total number of applicants, the total number of NGO donated, and the pie chart of specific and anonymous individuals and other data visualization such as bar graphs.

F. DATA VALIDATION/DOCUMENT VERIFICATION

A criterion and a feature of EduCash that validates and verifies the data that is being sent or submitted into the platform.

G. DONOR PORTAL/DONOR PROFILE.

A criterion of EduCash that refers to the personalized space of donors in the platform.

H. EDUCASH.

A platform that aims to connect donors and underprivileged and deserving college students that are studying in Bacolod City.

I. MONETARY DONATIONS .

It refers to one of the scopes of the platform that means the donations are only accepted is in a form of money.

J. NON-GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATIONS.

An actor of EduCash that provides financial support to students through monetary donations using payment gateways.

K. PAYMENT GATEWAYS.

A criterion of EduCash that refers to the means of financial transactions in the platform, examples are PayPal, Gcash, Maya, and Bank Payment Integration.

L. SCHOLARSHIP AGENCIES.

An actor of EduCash who receives the donations before distributing it to the students and providing students educational opportunities.

M. SCHOLARSHIP MATCH.

A feature of EduCash that allows students to match their credentials to scholarship agencies and provide them an application form.

N. SECURITY MEASURES.

A criterion of EduCash that is employed to protect sensitive data and the privacy of students, also safeguarding transactions from one server to another.

O. UNDERPRIVILEGED AND DESERVING COLLEGE STUDENTS /
RECIPIENTS

An actor of EduCash that receives the calculated monetary donations from donor as financial support for their education.

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USERS' MANUAL

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USER MANUAL

This section provides users with step-by-step guidance on how to navigate and use the different modules of the application. It includes screenshots of the system interface accompanied by clear descriptions to help users better understand how the web application functions. The manual consists of detailed explanations of text fields, buttons, dropdown menus, and other interface elements to support ease of use. The application accessed through its official website, educash.com, and for optimal performance, a stable internet connection with a minimum speed of 25 Mb/s is recommended.

1. Login Page

EduCash is open to all users who wish to use the application. For those who already have an account, logging in is quick and seamless users simply enter their registered credentials to access the system and explore its features. Screenshot 1 presents the login interface and serves as a guide for the required inputs.

Screenshot 1. EduCash Login Interface.

- A. Email Text Field – A text field provided for the users to type their registered user credentials.
- B. Password Text Field – A text field where users input the password associated with their account.
- C. Remember me Checkbox – A checkbox that allows the system to remember the users login credentials, making future logins faster without requiring the user to re-enter their information.
- D. Eye Shaped Icon – An icon that users toggles to show or hide the password entered in the password field.
- E. Forgot Password Link – A link that redirects users to the forgot password interface, allowing them to reset their password if needed.
- F. Sign In Button – A button that users click after completing the required fields to log in to their account.
- G. Create Student Account Button – A button provided for users who wish to register as a student and do not yet have an account.
- H. Create Donor Account Button – A button intended for individuals, organizations, or entities who want to register as donors in the application.
- I. Create Agency Account Button – A button used by scholarship agencies to register and create an official agency account within the system.

2. Forgot Password

As shown in Screenshot 2, the application provides a user-friendly “Forgot Password” interface for users who have forgotten their account credentials. Through this feature, users enter their registered email address to initiate the password recovery process. Once the Send Password Reset Link button is selected, the system automatically sends a reset link to the provided email address, directing users to a dedicated interface for securely resetting their password.

Screenshot 2. Forgot Password Interface

- A. Email Text Field - A text field where users enter their registered email address to receive a verification code for password recovery.

- B. Send Code Button – A button that sends a verification code to the email address provided by the user.
- C. Verify It Button – A button that confirms the entered email address and proceeds to the next step of the password recovery process.
- D. Back to Sign in Link – A link that redirects the user back to the sign-in page of the application.
- E. Code Text Field – A text field where users input the verification code sent to their email address.
- F. Verify Code Button – A button that validates the entered verification code and allows the user to continue with resetting their password.
- G. Resend Code Link – A link that allows users to request a new verification code if the previous one has expired or was not received.
- H. Back to Sign in Link – A link that returns the user to the login page at any point during the verification process.

Screenshot 3. Verification Code

3. Student Registration Page

As shown in Screenshot 3, The Student Registration Page allows new users to easily create a student account within the application. This page provides clearly labeled input fields where students enter their personal and academic information, such as their full name, school, program, and contact details. The registration process is simple and user friendly, guiding students through each required step until all information is successfully submitted. Once completed, students are granted access to the systems functionalities.

The screenshot shows a registration form titled "Create a Student Account". The form is organized into two columns of input fields. The first column contains: "Full Name" (labeled A), "Contact." (labeled B), "Email" (labeled C), and "Password" (labeled D). The second column contains: "Search School" (labeled E), "Search Program" (labeled F), a date field with a calendar icon and placeholder "mm/dd/yyyy" (labeled G), and "Confirm Password" (labeled H). Below these fields is a "Continue" button (labeled I) and a "Sign in" link (labeled J) with the text "Already have an account? Sign in".

Screenshot 3. Student Registration Interface.

A. Full Name – A text field where users enter their complete legal name for account registration.

- B. Contact – A text field where users provide their active contact number for communication purposes.
- C. Email – A text field where users input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Password – A text field where users create a secure password for their account.
- E. Search School – A search field that allows users to find and select the educational institution where they are currently enrolled.
- F. Select Program – A dropdown menu where users choose their current program or course of study.
- G. Select Birthday – A date selector that allows users to choose their date of birth.
- H. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- I. Continue Button – A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- J. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

4. Upload Credentials Form

As shown in Screenshot 4, The Upload Credentials Interface provides students with a structured way to submit the required documents for verification. Each upload field is clearly labeled to help users attach the correct files without confusion. The interface guides students through the process step by step, ensuring that all required documents are

completed before submission. Once the documents are uploaded, students submit their credentials for review and validation by the system.

Screenshot 4. Upload Credentials Interface

- A. Upload Certified True Copy of Grades – A file upload field where students submit an official and certified copy of their academic grades for verification.
- B. Upload Certificate of Enrollment – A file upload field used to submit proof that the student is currently enrolled in an educational institution.
- C. Upload Validated School ID – A file upload field where students upload a valid school identification card to confirm their student status.
- D. Upload Certificate of Indigency – A file upload field for submitting an official document that certifies the student’s financial need.
- E. Upload Proof of Income – A file upload field where students provide documents showing the income of their parent or guardian for financial assessment.
- F. Submit Button – A button that submits all uploaded documents for system validation and review

5. Student Profile

As shown in Screenshot 5, Student Profile Interface provides students with a convenient space to manage and update their personal information within the application. Through this interface, students upload or edit their profile photo, allowing them to personalize their account. It also includes options for updating credentials, where students submit or modify required documents such as proof of income for verification. Changes made in the profile saved using the submit button to ensure that updated information is properly applied.

Screenshot 5. Student Profile Interface

- A. Upload Photo – A file upload option that allows users to add or change their profile photo within the application.
- B. Submit Button – A button used to save and apply the uploaded photo or updated information.
- C. Update Credentials Button – A button that redirects users to the credentials page, that allows students to upload or modify required documents.
- D. Edit Photo Button – A button that allows users to replace or update their existing profile photo.
- E. Upload Proof of Income – A file upload field where users submit an updated proof of income document for verification purposes.

6. Matched Scholarships

As shown Screenshot 6, The Matched Scholarships Interface serves as a results page where students are presented with scholarship opportunities generated by the system based on their submitted credentials. This interface automatically filters available scholarships using eligibility criteria such as academic standing, financial need, and personal background. Students views all scholarships that match their credentials in one consolidated list.

Screenshot 6. Matched Scholarships Interface

A. Apply now - A button that allows users to start the scholarship application process.

7. Application Form

As shown in Screenshot 7, application essay interface provides a form for students to fill out and submit to the scholarship agency. The application form provides a question to the student of why is that student deserve the scholarship. To guide the students of the number of words that is currently being typed, a word counter below at the bottom right side of the text-area is provided.

Why do you deserve this Scholarship? (Please write a minimum of 200 words)

I believe I deserve this scholarship because I am committed to achieving academic excellence while using my education to create meaningful impact in my community. Throughout my academic journey, I have consistently demonstrated dedication, perseverance, and a strong work ethic, even in the face of financial challenges. My passion for learning drives me to continuously improve myself, not only for personal success but also to contribute to the betterment of society.

Receiving this scholarship would greatly ease my financial burden, allowing me to focus more on my studies and participate in academic and community initiatives that foster growth and development. I plan to use my knowledge and skills to help address pressing issues in my community, such as improving access to education and creating opportunities for underprivileged youth.

This scholarship represents more than just financial assistance; it is an opportunity to further develop my potential, enhance my leadership abilities, and give back to those who have supported me along the way. I am determined to maximize this opportunity and uphold the values of hard work, responsibility, and service. With your support, I can continue striving toward my academic goals and become a positive force for change. Thank you and God Bless!

Words: 201

B → **Submit Application**

Screenshot 7. Application Essay Interface

- A. Essay Form Text field – A text field that allows student to input their scholarship essay.
- B. Submit Application – A button that allows the student to send their completed scholarship application and essay to the scholarship agency for review.

8. Student Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 8, Student Inbox interface provides student the notification that the application sent by the student has been approved together with the disclaimer notice that the student is not an official scholar of the agency outside of the application. The interface also shows the financial transactions of the allowance distribution. The transaction shows the transaction id, and the message that the student has received the distribution together with the amount, the name of the agency, the payment gateway used.

Screenshot 8. Student Inbox Interface.

- A. Acknowledge – A button that allows students to let the donor know that the money has been received.
- B. View – A button that allows student to view the receipt of the transaction.

9. Student Files Section

As shown in Screenshot 9, Student Files Section interface provides students the credentials section page where uploaded files are located. In the interface, there are five documents that are shown namely the grades, the certificate of enrolment, the validated school ID, the certificate of indigency of the student, together with the tax exemption certificate.

Your Uploaded Files			
Documents			Action

Screenshot 9. Uploaded Files Interface

- A. View Grades – A button that allows to view the transcript or report card showing academic performance.
- B. View Certificate of Enrollment - A button that allows to view the official document proving current enrollment.
- C. View School ID - A button that allows to view the valid student identification card.
- D. View Certificate of Indigency - A button that allows to view the document certifying financial status.

E. View Certificate of Tax Exemption - A button that allows to view the official document indicating any tax exemptions.

10. Donor Registration Page

As shown in Screenshot 10, The Donor Registration Page allows new users to easily create a donor account within the application. This page provides clearly labeled input fields where Donors enter their name, contact number, email address, and password. A dropdown menu for donor type is provided where they are able to decide whether anonymous, individual, NGO, government, or private companies for the donor type.

The screenshot shows a donor registration form with the following elements:

- A:** Enter Name (Name of Donor)
- B:** Enter Contact (Contact no.)
- C:** Enter Email (e.g Example@gmail.com)
- D:** Select Donor Type (Private Companies)
- E:** Enter Password (Password)
- F:** Confirm Password
- G:** Continue button
- H:** Already have an account? Log in button

Screenshot 10. Donor Registration Interface.

- A. Name – A text field where donors enter their complete legal name for account registration.
- B. Contact – A text field where donors provide their active contact number for communication purposes.

- C. Email – A text field where donors input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Select Donor Type – A dropdown A dropdown field where donor choose whether anonymous, individual, NGO, government, or private companies.
- E. Password – A text field where donors create a secure password for their account.
- F. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- G. Continue - A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- H. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

11. Donor Navigation Bar

As shown in Screenshot 11, Primary donor interface, serving as the central hub for donors. In this interface donors manage their account and access key features of the application. It allows donors to view and edit their profile information, make donations, check reports, and communicate through the inbox. Navigation options are clearly displayed to help users move between different sections efficiently. The interface also provides tools for updating profile details, including uploading a profile photo and saving changes.

Screenshot 11. Donor Navigation Bar Interface

- A. Profile – A navigation option that allows donors to view and manage their personal account information.
- B. Donate – navigation button that redirects donors to the donation page, where they contribute funds to selected beneficiaries or programs.
- C. Reports – A section where donors views records and summaries of their donation activities.
- D. Inbox - A messaging feature that allows donors to receive updates, notifications, and messages within the application.
- E. Upload Photo - A file upload option that allows donors to add or change their profile photo.

F. Save Button - A button used to save and apply any changes made to the donor's profile information.

G. Edit Profile - A button that enables donors to modify their personal details and update profile information.

12. Donate Matching

As shown in Screenshot 12, the application provides donors with a search function that allows them to find scholarship agencies by filling out the location of the scholarship agency and the minimum average requirement required in the scholarship agency and click on the search button

The screenshot displays a search interface for finding scholarship agencies. At the top, there are two dropdown menus: 'Enter Location of Agency' (labeled A) and 'Enter Minimum Average Requirement' (labeled B, currently set to '75% - 79%'). Below these is a 'Search' button (labeled C). The results section, titled 'List of Verified Scholarship Agencies', shows three agencies: 'EduCash' (Tulong Dunong), 'LGU', and 'Department of Science and Technology'.

Screenshot 12. Donate Matching Interface

A. Enter Location of Agency – A text field where donors input the location of the scholarship agency to narrow down search results.

- B. Enter Average Requirement – A dropdown field where donors the select minimum average grade requirement set by the scholarship agency.
- C. Search Button - A button that initiates the search process and displays scholarship agencies that match the entered criteria.

13. Searched Scholarship Agencies

As shown in Screenshot 13, the filtered scholarship agencies are displayed in a card-based layout for easy viewing. Each card presents the name of the scholarship agency along with its profile picture to help donors identify the organization. The interface provides action buttons that allow donors to interact with each scholarship agency. By selecting the appropriate option, donors either view additional details or proceed with the donation process.

Screenshot 13. Donation Interface

- A. View Button – A button that displays the list of students associated with the selected scholarship agency.
- B. Donate Button – A button that allows donors to proceed with the donation process for the selected scholarship agency.

14. Payment Methods

As shown in Screenshot 14, the application provides a payment gateway that allows donors to complete their donations using available digital payment methods. This interface displays the supported payment options, enabling donors to select their preferred method and proceed with the transaction securely. Once a payment option is chosen, the system guides the donor through the necessary steps to successfully complete the donation process.

Screenshot 14. Payment Gateways Interface

- A. Gcash button– A payment option that allows donors to complete their donation using the GCash e-wallet.
- B. Paypal button – A payment option that enables donors to donate securely through their PayPal account.
- C. Maya button – A payment option that allows donors to make donations using the Maya digital wallet.

15. Upload Receipt Form

As shown in Screenshot 15, the application provides donors with an interface for uploading the transaction receipt after completing the payment. This interface allows donors to submit proof of payment to confirm that the donation has been successfully made. Once the receipt is uploaded, the system sends the transaction details to the selected scholarship agency for verification.

Screenshot 15. Upload Receipt Interface

- A. Choose File button - A button that allows donors to select and attach the payment receipt for upload.
- B. Upload Receipt button - A button that allows donors to submit the payment receipt to complete and confirm the donation transaction.

16. Donor Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 16, This interface displays a complete record of all donations made by the donor through the application. The donation history is presented in a tabular format. Above the table, two dropdown filter options are provided. These filters allow the donor to customize the displayed donation records based on the selected scholarship agency and the month of donation.

The screenshot displays the 'Donation History' interface. At the top, there are two dropdown filters: 'All Agencies' (labeled A) and 'All Months' (labeled B). Below the filters is a table with the following data:

Donation ID	Amount	Agency	Date of Donation
67	₱46,000.00	SM Foundation	May 27, 2025
68	₱46,000.00	Mcdo Agency	May 27, 2025
72	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
73	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 24, 2025
74	₱50,000.00	Bacolod Agency	July 31, 2025
75	₱50,000.00	LGU	August 24, 2025

Total Donation: ₱292,000.00

Screenshot 16. Donor Donation Inbox Interface

- A. Name of agencies - This is a dropdown field that allows the donor to select a specific scholarship agency.
- B. Date of transaction - This is a dropdown field that enables the donor to select a specific month.

17. Student List

As shown in screenshot 17, this interface displays the list of students under the selected scholarship agency. The list of students is presented in a tabular format, showing their academic information. Above the table, a school selection dropdown and a program search input field are provided. The school selection dropdown allows the donor to choose a specific school, filtering the list to display only students currently enrolled in the selected school.

The screenshot shows a web interface for viewing scholars. At the top, there are two search fields: 'School:' with a dropdown menu currently set to 'All' (labeled A), and 'Program:' with a text input field 'Search program' (labeled B). To the right of the 'Program:' field are two buttons: a green 'Filter' button (labeled C) and a grey 'Return' button (labeled D). Below the search fields is a table with three columns: 'Scholar Name', 'School', and 'Program of Study'. The table contains seven rows of student data.

Scholar Name	School	Program of Study
Adrian Magallanes	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Zachary Guzon	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Ern Jan	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Karen Kaye Alfonso	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	BS Computer Science
Wrenz Bancolo	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing
Von Andrei Awacay	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Information Technology
Dorothy Abanalo	University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos (UNO-R)	Entertainment and Multimedia Computing

Screenshot17. View Scholars Interface

- A. School Selection – This is a drop-down menu that allows the donor to select a specific school where the students are currently enrolled.
- B. Search Program – This is a search input field that enables the donor to search and filter students based on their program of study.
- C. Filter – This button submits the selected criteria from the school drop-down menu and the program search field.
- D. Return – This button redirects the donor back to the previous page.

18. Scholarship Agency Registration

As shown in Screenshot 18, the Scholarship Agency Registration interface enables organizations to create a scholarship agency account by entering basic information such as agency name, contact number, email address, and password. The process is simple and user-friendly, guiding agencies through the required steps. Once submitted, the registration request is sent to the administrator for validation and approval before full system access is granted.

The screenshot shows a registration form with the following elements:

- A**: Name of Scholarship Agency (input field)
- B**: Contact (input field)
- C**: Email (input field)
- D**: Password (input field)
- E**: Confirm Password (input field)
- F**: Continue (button)
- G**: Already have an Account? Login (link)

Screenshot 18. Scholarship Agency Registration Interface.

- A. Name – A text field where scholarship agencies enter their complete agency name for account registration.
- B. Contact – A text field where scholarship agency provides their active contact number for communication purposes.
- C. Email – A text field where scholarship agency input a valid email address to be used as their login credential and for account verification.
- D. Password – A text field where donors create a secure password for their account.
- E. Confirm Password – A text field where users re-enter their password to prevent errors.
- F. Continue - A button that submits the entered information and proceeds to the next step of the registration process.
- G. Already Have an Account – A link that redirects users back to the sign-in page if they already have an existing account.

Screenshot 18. Email Verification Code.

A. Email Verification – A button that verifies the entered email address.

19. Scholarship Agency Navigation Bar

As shown in Screenshot 19, this interface serves as the primary dashboard for the scholarship agency, acting as the central hub for managing activities within the application. It allows scholarship agency to view and edit their profile information. The navigation panel provides access to key features such as Post, Profile, Criteria, Reports, Inbox, Donation History, and Calculation, enabling efficient movement between different sections of the system.

Screenshot 19. Scholarship Agency Navigation Bar Interface

A. Post – A navigation option that allows users to create announcements, updates, or messages visible to relevant parties.

- B. Profile – A navigation option that allows users to view and manage their personal and academic account information.
- C. Criteria – A section where users view the eligibility or selection standards for scholarships or programs.
- D. Reports – A section where users view the summaries and analytics of activities, donations, or scholarship distribution.
- E. Inbox – A messaging feature that allows users to receive updates, notifications, and messages within the application.
- F. Donation History – A section where the records of all past donations, including amounts, dates, and recipients.
- G. Calculation – A section where the calculate scholarship distribution, allocate donations, and analyze related numerical data.
- H. Upload Photo – A file upload option that allows users to change their profile picture.
- I. Save – A button used to save and apply any changes made to forms, profiles, or entries.
- J. Edit Profile – A button that enables users to modify their personal information and update profile details.
- K. Upload Certificate – A file upload option that allows users to submit academic or achievement certificates.
- L. View Scholars – A dropdown field where users view list of scholars filtered by school via a drop-down menu.

M. View Files – A section that provides access to uploaded documents, certificates, or reports.

20. Scholarship Matching Form

As shown in Screenshot 20, this feature allows the scholarship agency to match students to scholarships. The matching is based on the criteria previously set, including Location, Minimum Average Requirement, Supported Institutions, Tuition Coverage, Deadline of Application, and Coverage Type. These criteria ensure that only eligible students are paired with the appropriate scholarships. The interface gives a clear view of candidates, making efficient selection.

Screenshot 20. Scholarship Matching Form Interface

A. Location – Specifies the geographic area where eligible applicants must reside or study.

- B. Minimum Average Requirement – A dropdown field that indicates the required minimum academic average or GPA for applicants.
 - C. Supported Institutions - This field indicates the types of educational institutions supported by the application, including both public and private schools.
 - D. Tuition Coverage – A dropdown field that defines the portion or percentage of tuition fees covered by the scholarship
 - E. Deadline of Application – A date selector that state the final date for submitting scholarship applications.
 - F. Coverage Type – A dropdown field that describes the type of financial support provided.
 - G. Set Criteria – A button that allows the scholarship provider to define additional eligibility requirements.
 - H. Post a Scholarship – A button used to confirm and publish the scholarship listing based on the defined criteria.
21. Scholarship Posting Form

As shown in Screenshot 21, the application provides an interface for the scholarship agency to manage scholarship information. The agency inputs details about the scholarship benefits, including tuition coverage and inclusions. It also allows the agency to set eligibility requirements, application requirements, and the application process. The form includes fields for the submission deadline and announcement of results, ensuring clarity for applicants.

Set Information About the Scholarship

Set Scholarship Benefits

Enter Tuition Coverage
35000.00 above **A**

Scholarship Inclusion

Monthly Living Allowance
 Book and Educational Materials Allowance
 One-Time Laptop or Gadget Grant
 Internet and Communication Support
 Thesis or Research Grant **B**
 Internship or Mentorship Opportunities
 Exclusive Training and Workshops
 Health and Wellness Support
 Employment Assistance After Graduation
Other: _____

Set Eligibility Requirement

Degree Preference Related to

Science, Technology and Mathematics **F**
 Education
 Arts and Humanities
 Agriculture and Forestry
 Business, Hospitality and Finance
Other: _____

Minimum Average Requirement
75% - 80% **G**

Set Application Requirement

Certified True Copy of Grades or Transcript of Records **C**
 Certificate of Enrolment or Admission
 Copy of Valid School ID
 Income Tax Return (ITR) of parents/guardian
 Certificate of Indigency from Barangay or Municipality
 Latest Payslip of Parents/Guardian
 Certificate of Non-filing of Income Tax
 Birth Certificate
 Parent's or Guardian's Valid ID
 Medical Certificate
 Barangay Clearance or Good Moral Certificate
Other: _____

Deadline of Submission **D**
mm/dd/yyyy

Announcement of Result **E**
mm/dd/yyyy

Set Application Process

Set the Application Process in order

1 Enter process 1 here **H**

2

Submit **I**

[Set a Matching Criteria? Click Here](#) **J**

Screenshot 21. Scholarship Posting Interface

- A. Tuition Coverage – A dropdown field where the scholarship agency specifies the tuition fees covered by the scholarship.
- B. Scholarship Inclusion – A field used to list additional benefits included in the scholarship, such as allowances or other forms of support.
- C. Set Application Requirement – A field where the agency defines the documents and qualifications required from applicants.
- D. Deadline of Submission – A date selector where the agency sets the final date for submitting scholarship applications.
- E. Announcement of Result – A date selector that indicates when the results of the scholarship application be released.
- F. Degree Preference – A field where the agency specifies preferred degree programs eligible for the scholarship.

- G. Minimum Average Requirement – A dropdown field where the agency sets the minimum academic average required for applicants.
- H. Set Application Process – A field that allows the agency outlines the steps applicants must follow during the application process.
- I. Submit – A button used to save and publish the scholarship information entered by the agency.
- J. Click here – A links that redirects the scholarship agency to the scholarship matching criteria.

22. Scholarship Agency Inbox

As shown in Screenshot 22, the Inbox interface allows scholarship agencies to manage scholarship applications and received donations. It displays a list of pending applicants with options to view and validate applications, as well as a donations list showing donor details, dates, payment methods, amounts, and receipts. Action buttons enable agencies to acknowledge or delete donation records.

Applications						
Student Name	Date Submitted	Action				
Adrian Magallanes	2025-12-25 12:49:29	<input type="button" value="View"/>				

Donations						
Donor Name	Date of Donation	Payment Method	Amount	Receipt	Action	
Libertad NGO	2025-11-15 15:08:21	gcash	P1415.00	<input type="button" value="View"/>	<input type="button" value="Acknowledge"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Libertad NGO	2025-10-31 07:50:58	gcash	P60000.00	<input type="button" value="View"/>	<input type="button" value="Acknowledge"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Libertad NGO	2025-10-15 14:54:52	gcash	P10000.00	<input type="button" value="View"/>	<input type="button" value="Acknowledge"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Libertad NGO	2025-08-24 07:37:06	gcash	P50000.00	<input type="button" value="View"/>	<input type="button" value="Acknowledge"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Libertad NGO	2025-07-24 07:33:31	gcash	P50000.00	<input type="button" value="View"/>	<input type="button" value="Acknowledge"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>

Screenshot 22. Scholarship Agency Inbox Interface

- A. View Applicant – A button that allows scholarship agencies to view applicant details and continue the application validation process.
- B. View receipt – A button that displays the uploaded transaction receipt for the selected donation.
- C. Acknowledge – A button used to confirm and acknowledge receipt of the donation.
- D. Delete – A button that removes the selected donation record from the system.

23. Calculation Method

As shown in Screenshot 23, the system provides multiple remittance calculation methods for scholarship distribution. These include Top 20 Percent, Top 30 Percent, Top 10, Top 20, and Divided Equally, each determining how donation amounts are allocated based on academic performance or equal sharing. The selected method automatically calculates and distributes the total donations according to the defined rules.

Scholar	Amount
Adrian Magallanes	₱8,823.53
Zachary Gutan	₱8,823.53
Em Jan	₱8,823.53
Karen Kaye Alfonso	₱8,823.53
Wrenz Barcoalo	₱8,823.53
Von Andrei Awacay	₱8,823.53
Dorothy Abanilo	₱8,823.53
Niel Yuri Adolfo	₱8,823.53
Antonio Camacho	₱8,823.53
Jeptha Osorio	₱8,823.53

Screenshot 44. Calculation Method

- A. Selection of Calculation - Allows the scholarship agency to choose the preferred calculation method for distributing donations.
- B. Approve Distribution - Confirms and applies the selected calculation method to proceed with the fund distribution.

In conclusion, EduCash provides a comprehensive user guide the users through the various interfaces and functionalities of the application. The succeeding sections, including the student registration process, credential upload interface, donor and scholarship agency dashboards, donation workflow, and inbox management, highlight the systems core features and capabilities. With a strong emphasis on usability, security, and efficient information management, it is designed to support students, donors, and scholarship agencies in a seamless and organized manner. Overall, the application aims to deliver an accessible, reliable, and transparent platform for managing scholarships and financial assistance. The structured presentation of system interfaces reinforces clarity and consistency across different user roles, promoting ease of navigation and reduced operational errors. Clear workflows and well-defined processes further contribute to efficient coordination among stakeholders involved in scholarship management.

APPENDIX A

Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.
(Adopted from *Philippine Association of Institutions for Research (PAIR), Inc.*)

WE, the researcher, and research adviser/consultant, have worked together in a capstone project from August 2024 to May 2025.

WE have used various forms of contact during the capstone project work such as Microsoft Teams, Facebook and other means of communication.

WE agree that :

- the academic partnership leads to publication of the manuscript with the research consultant as the author and the researcher, the primary author.
- the paper be presented in public forum by the researcher if available at such an opportunity or by the research adviser/consultant if the researcher is no longer around.
- only the name of the oral presenter shall be submitted to the Conference organizer.

WE agree to dress formally and prepare adequately for the formal oral presentation in both the oral defense panel and the public presentations.

Signed this 27th of July in the year of our Lord 2025 in Bacolod City, Philippines.

Von Andrei G. Awacay
Researcher

Christine Joy S. Dorias
Technical Consultant

Jhon Patrick B. Perez
Researcher

Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.
Course Adviser

Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
Researcher

Mark Angelo C. Navarro
Witness

APPENDIX B

EduCash Concept Paper.

Capstone Project Concept Title	EduCash		
Concept Author and Collaborator(s)	Jhon Patrick B. Perez	Von Andrei G. Awacay	Jonh Lorence G. Reyes
	Main Author	Collaborator #1	Collaborator #2
Rationale of the Capstone Project Concept			
<p>EduCash is an online system carefully designed to respond to the financial challenges of less privileged but worthy college students in Bacolod City in response to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education. It overcomes systemic barriers in access to higher education by providing connections between students and donors, NGOs, and private individuals who are willing to give out finances. Its focus is on ensuring equity in access to education, marking a commitment toward fostering academic excellence and reducing economic constraints. Facilitating a smooth interface for matching scholarships, making financial transactions, and interactions between donors and students, EduCash acts as a revolutionary tool empowering students to achieve their academic dreams while promoting participation by the community in education.</p>			
Main Features and Functionalities			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Document Verification – Upon registration, users are required to submit valid documents. These documents are verified using this feature to prevent fraudulent data in the platform. 2. Scholarship Match – This feature allows students to connect to scholarship agency, providing them efficient inquiry by matching their credentials to whatever scholarship agency they are suitable/ 3. Donor portal – this feature provides a personalized space for donors where they can track and send donations to scholarship agencies. 4. Data Analytics - This data analytics feature displayed in a dashboard consists of the data such as total amount of donations gathered, total number of applicants, total number of NGO donors, which are represented in a bar graph, and a pie chart of the percentage of the individual and anonymous donors. This feature will serve as a significant element for evaluating the performance of the platform. Generation of comprehensive reports to provide users a valuable awareness of the operation and impact of the platform. Specifically, the platform provides an analyzation and display key metrics that will be discussed further in this section of the paper. 5. Allowance Distribution - In this feature, the students can claim financial aid calculated by the platform through payment gateways integrated in the platform. The distribution will be scheduled on a specific month each semester and each time before the distribution, students must submit their academic performance. Students must maintain their academic performance as for the eligibility criteria to avoid being dropped as a recipient of the platform. Reaching below the criteria will result to drop automatically from the platform. 			
Project Usability / Benefit Justification			
<p>This platform is useful for both students, and scholarship agencies. Using this platform, scholarship agencies can cater to students who really deserves to be granted with financial support since students that are catered by the platform are only those who excel in their academic performance. The platform also motivates the students to be committed in their education since the platform has a retention policy.</p>			
Relevance to the Theme			
EduCash aligns with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing Goal 4 (Quality Education)			
Technology Deployment			
<p>Frontend: HTML/, CSS, BOOTSTRAP, JavaScript. Backend: MySQL, Python, Django. Search Engine: Google</p>			
Anticipated Challenges			
<p>One major challenge for the project team would be the donor and agency engagement. without these actors, the platform cannot do what it is programmed for since the platform relies on donors as it is a fundraising platform.</p>			

APPENDIX C

PERT Table.

Act Codes	Activity	Predecessor	Duration (Weeks)
A	Project Conceptualization	None	1
B	Identify Project Requirements	A	1
C	Identify and Reviewing of Related Systems	B	3
D	Identify Software and Hardware Requirements	C	1
E	Identify System Features	D	3
F	Design Prototyping	E	3
G	Frontend Development	F	16
H	Backend Development	F	21
I	Testing and debugging	H	2
J	Final Documentation	I	1

APPENDIX D

PERT Diagram.

APPENDIX E

Gantt Chart.

APPENDIX F

Project Cost.

PROJECT COST	YEARLY COST	SERVICE
Internet	Php 15,588.00	PLDT WIFI
Prototype	Php P4,265.00	Canva/Figma
Content	Php 1,387.00	Grammarly
TOTAL SYSTEM COST	Php 21,240.00	
System Support and Maintenance	Php 2,000.00	Cloud Services
Tools	Php 1,500.00	APIs Services
OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE COST	Php 3,500.00	

APPENDIX G

Cost Benefit Analysis.

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Total System Cost	₱21,240.00					
Operation and Maintenance Cost	₱0.00	₱3,500.00	₱3,850.00	₱4,235.00	₱4,658.50	₱5,124.35
Discount Factor (12%)	1.00	0.87	0.80	0.71	0.64	0.57
Time Adjusted Cost	₱21,240.00	₱3,045.00	₱3,080.00	₱3,006.85	₱2,981.44	₱2,920.88
Cumulative Time Adjusted Cost	₱21,240.00	₱24,285.00	₱27,365.00	₱30,371.85	₱33,353.29	₱36,274.17
Benefits derived from operation of New System	₱0.00	₱50,000.00	₱55,000.00	₱60,500.00	₱66,550.00	₱73,205.00
Discount Factor (12%)	1.00	0.87	0.80	0.71	0.64	0.57
Time Adjusted Benefits	₱0.00	₱43,500.00	₱44,000.00	₱42,955.00	₱42,592.00	₱41,726.85
Cumulative Time Adjusted Benefits	₱0.00	₱43,500.00	₱87,500.00	₱130,455.00	₱173,047.00	₱214,773.85
Cumulative Time Adjusted Cost + Benefits	₱21,240.00	₱19,215.00	₱60,135.00	₱100,083.15	₱139,693.71	₱178,499.68

Return of Investments (ROI)	491.52%
Net Present Value (NPV)	Php 178,499.68
Payback Period	0.49 years

APPENDIX H

Product Logo.

The EduCash logo symbolizes empowering individuals through education and financial support for their educational journeys. The person with graduation cap represents the pursuit of knowledge, wisdom, and aspiring students for academic success and to move forward seeking greater success. The green in "Cash" symbolizes growth and financial wellbeing, indicating opportunities. The typeface combines the words "Edu" which is short for education and "Cash" which is for financial support emphasizing the linking of knowledge with funds. The broken line circle with arrow symbolizes the distribution of the funds. The green cash icon symbolizes the effectiveness of the distribution of funding meeting the educational requirements of students.

APPENDIX I

Team Logo.

The "Triple Transcendence" symbolizes beyond limits through the combined strength of three interconnected forces. The typography of "Triple Transcendence" serves as the anchor of the logo, ensuring a sturdy visual identity. The logo visually represents unity, growth, and progress through its design elements. The three human Figures represent three of us indicating teamwork, self-determination, and stability. The upward motion of the Figure highlights growth and collective success of the team. The three arches on the top signify movement and progress. The Figures and arches work together to convey harmony, forward motion, and the idea of surpassing limits.

APPENDIX J

Product Packaging.

APPENDIX K

Product Poster.

EduCash
Your Bridge to a Brighter Academic Future

It is a web-based application that links donors and scholarship agencies with financially challenged yet deserving college students in Bacolod City. It offers a transparent platform for donations, guarantees proper fund distribution, and connects students with scholarship opportunities, enabling them to pursue their education without financial obstacles.

It matches qualified students with scholarship agencies based on set academic and financial criteria.

SYSTEM FEATURES

- DATA ANALYTICS**: It provides reports and visual insights on donations, donors, and applicants to track system performance.
- SCHOLARSHIP MATCHING**: It matches qualified students with scholarship agencies based on set academic and financial criteria.
- DOCUMENT VERIFICATION**: It validates uploaded student documents to ensure authenticity and prevent fraudulent applications.
- ALLOWANCE CALCULATION**: It calculates how student allowances are distributed, using a one-time selection of the preferred calculation method.
- DONOR PORTAL**: It allows donors to contribute funds securely through multiple payment gateways and receive transaction receipts.

TECHNOLOGIES: HTML, PHP, MySQL

Contact us: educash@gmail.com
Visit us: educash.com

DEVELOPER BY:
Von Andrei Awacay
Ihon Patrick Perez
Jonh Lawrence Reyes

APPENDIX L

Integrity Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Only users are able to alter their personal information.	Resolved
When editing user information, users must provide their password for confirmation.	Not Resolved
Administrators are able to alter user information	Not Resolved
When trying to access the “forgot password” feature, an email confirmation is sent to the users.	Resolved
$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $I = \frac{2}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	50%

Financial Transactions	
Requirements	Status
Only scholarship agencies are able to see the total amount that they received	Resolved
Donations are recorded	Resolved
Student receives the donation	Resolved
Every donation has system generated receipt	Not Resolved
Receipts are sent to the recipients for acknowledgement	Resolved
Total amount for each scholarship agencies is updated	Resolved
$I = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $I = \frac{5}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	50%

APPENDIX M

Confidentiality Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Users must register an account	Resolved
The users must be verified before they are able to access the features	Resolved
Passwords are hashed in the database	Not Resolved
Email verifications are only sent to email provided	Resolved
$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CF = \frac{3}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

Financial Transactions	
Requirements	Status
System keeps the contact information of donors	Resolved
Donors are able to stay anonymous	Resolved
Receipts are not modifiable	Resolved
Receipts are only visible to donor and recipient	Resolved
Only donors can view their donation history	Resolved
Donors are not able to see the total amount of donation per agency	Resolved
$CF = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CF = \frac{6}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

APPENDIX N

Authenticity Score Computation.

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Email and Username are found in the database	Resolved
Age restrictions	Not Resolved
Passwords match with the email provided	Resolved
Password complexity	Resolved
Password recovery	Not Resolved
Session Timeout	Resolved
Multiple devices logged in	Resolved
Multiple tabs logged in	Not Resolved
$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $AU = \frac{5}{8} \times 100$	
Mean Score	62.5%

Account Creation and Management	
Requirements	Status
Donation amounts are saved in the database	Resolved
Amount restrictions	Not Resolved
Clarity of receipts	Resolved
Duplicate donations	Resolved
Amount extraction in receipts	Resolved
Confirmation	Not Resolved
$AU = \frac{\text{number of requirements resolved}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $AU = \frac{4}{6} \times 100$	
Mean Score	66.7%

APPENDIX O

Completeness Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Scholarship agencies are able to post deadlines	Complete
Match students based on the criteria set	Complete
Students are limited only to one scholarship	Not Complete
More than one matches are displayed for the students	Complete
Scholarship agencies are required to set criteria	Complete
Scholarship agencies set criteria only once	Not Complete
Scholarship agencies are notified about the matched student	Complete
Scholarship agencies are able to cross check the documents	Complete
$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CP = \frac{6}{8} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Scholarship agencies are able to choose a method of calculation	Complete
Overview of the calculation method before approval	Complete
Donors are informed about the method of calculation of each agency	Complete
Students are informed in the calculation method before receiving the money	Not Complete
$CP = \frac{\text{number of requirements completed}}{\text{total number of requirements}} \times 100$ $CP = \frac{3}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	75%

APPENDIX P

Correctness Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Submit button for criteria form	Correct
Submit button for postings form	Correct
Apply button for students	Correct
Error messages	Correct
Success messages	Correct
$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CR = \frac{5}{5} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Approve button for calculation dropdown	Correct
One calculation per period	Correct
Method of calculations	Correct
$CR = \frac{\text{number of correctly implemented functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CR = \frac{3}{3} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

APPENDIX Q

Consistency Score Computation.

Scholarship Matching and Postings	
Requirements	Status
Matches align with the criteria	Consistent
Students matched with scholarship agencies based on average required	Consistent
Procedures and guidelines are posted by scholarship agencies	Consistent
Users must be verified to use this feature	Consistent
$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CS = \frac{4}{4} \times 100$	
Mean Score	100%

Calculation	
Requirements	Status
Students receive the amount based on the calculation	Consistent
The calculation scales on the amount and the number of students	Consistent
All students are able to receive in all methods of calculation	Not Consistent
$CS = \frac{\text{number of consistent functions detected}}{\text{number of functions described in requirements specifications}} \times 100$ $CS = \frac{2}{3} \times 100$	
Mean Score	66.7%

APPENDIX R

Survey Result.

Criteria	Mean Score
Execution Efficiency	4.54
Code Simplicity	4.51
Communication Commonality	4.5
Security	4.5
Completeness	4.49
Data Commonality	4.48
Traceability	4.48
Expandability	4.46
Training	4.46
Controllability	4.45
Decomposability	4.45
Functional Simplicity	4.45
Instrumentation	4.44
Modularity	4.44
Self-Documentation	4.44
Auditability	4.43
Observability	4.42
Accuracy	4.41
Consistency and Understandability	4.41
Conciseness	4.39
Generality	4.38
Structural Simplicity	4.38
Operability	4.35
Software System Independence	4.35
Error Tolerance	4.34
Hardware Independence	4.29

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